

Bilaga 2

Ej tillgängliga och exkluderade och artiklar

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Ej tillgängliga artiklar

Dufosse K, Drewer J and Gabrielle B ; (2012). Soil carbon and N2O emission dynamics after destruction of a 20-year old Miscanthus stand, and comparison with a plot under annual crops. *Proceedings 20th ...*, pp..

Hernanz J L, Sánchez-Girón V and Navarrete L ;. (2009). Organic carbon balance in soil: long-term effect (1985-2005) of three tillage systems for a cereal/legume rotation, under semi-arid conditions of the Central Spanish Plateau. *Terralia (España)*, , pp..

Lazany J. (2003). Differences in soil carbon content in the treatments of Westik's crop rotation experiment. In: Natural resources and sustainable development. International scientific session and reviewed papers.. : , pp.119-120. function URL() { [native code] }.

Mikucioniene R and Aleinikoviene J . (2013). Pools of Soil Organic Carbon and Total Nitrogen in Long-term experiment on Gleyic Luvisols. In: Atkociuniene V, ed., *Rural Development 2013: Proceedings, Vol 6, Book 2*. Akademija: Aleksandras Stulginskis University, pp.177-181.

Exkluderade artiklar efter granskning av hela texten

Citation	Reason for exclusion
Abbott BW and Jones JB . (2015). Permafrost collapse alters soil carbon stocks, respiration, CH ₄ , and N ₂ O in upland tundra. <i>Global change biology</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Abdollahi L, Getahun G T and Munkholm L J;. (2017). Eleven Years' Effect of Conservation Practices for Temperate Sandy Loams: I. Soil Physical Properties and Topsoil Carbon Content. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 81(2), pp.380-391.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Cereal rotations only. No legumes (except in one out of eleven years) and no perennials. No eligible comparator.
Abodeely J M, Muth Jr and D J ; Koch J ; Bryden K M;. (2013). An integrated model approach for quantifying carbon emissions from residue-based biofuel production. In: . : American Society of Mechanical Engineers, pp.. Available at: function URL() { [native code] }.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Results not shown for individual rotations
Abou El-Nour, Mona M and Serry Soad Y;. (2018). Effect of Crop Sequence, Compost and Plant Residues on Majze Yield Production, Sandy Soil Fertility and Reduce N-Mineral Fertilizer. النباتية والبقايا والكمبوست المحصولي التعاقب تأثير. العضوي السماد استخدام تقليل و الرملية الأراضي وخصوبة الشامية الذرة إنتاج علي, 49(3), pp.141-162.	-Exclude on CLIMATE

Abril A, Casado-Murillo N and Vázquez C ; Olivera P ;. (2013). Labile and recalcitrant carbon in crop residue and soil under No-Till practices in central region of Argentina. <i>Open Agriculture Journal</i> , 7, pp.32-39.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Site 1 no comparator, site 2 and 3 in arid climate (Cwa and Bsk, respectively).
Adhikari P, Udawatta R P and Anderson S H;. (2014). Soil thermal properties under prairies, conservation buffers, and corn-soybean land use systems. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 78, pp.1977-1986.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Corn-soybean system vs. grass buffer (GB), agroforestry buffer (AGF), Tucker Prairie (TP), and Prairie Fork (PF) land use systems.
Aguilera E, Lassaletta L and Gattinger A ; ;. (2013). Managing soil carbon for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Mediterranean cropping systems: A meta-analysis. <i>Agriculture and Ecosystems & ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW
Aguilera J, Motavalli P and Valdivia C ; Gonzales M A;. (2013). Impacts of Cultivation and Fallow Length on Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Availability in the Bolivian Andean Highland Region. <i>Mountain Research and Development</i> , 33, pp.391-403.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Many different climate zones in nearby area, mostly wrong classes for us
Aguilera E, Guzman G and Alonso A ;. (2015). Greenhouse gas emissions from conventional and organic cropping systems in Spain. II. Fruit tree orchards. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i> , 35, pp.725-737.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Aher G, Cihacek L J and Cooper K ;. (2017). An evaluation of C and N on fresh and aged crop residue from mixed long-term no-till cropping systems. <i>Journal of Plant Nutrition</i> , 40, pp.177-186.	-Exclude on OUTCOME C in above-ground crop residues but not in soil.
Ahmad W, Singh B and Dijkstra FA ; Dalal RC ;. (2013). Inorganic and organic carbon dynamics in a limed acid soil are mediated by plants. <i>Soil Biology and Biochemistry</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Albaladejo J, Ortiz R and Garcia-Franco N ;. (2013). Land use and climate change impacts on soil organic carbon stocks in semi-arid Spain. <i>Journal of Soils and ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Bsk
Albizua A, Williams A and Hedlund K ; Pascual U ;. (2015). Crop rotations including ley and manure can promote ecosystem services in conventional farming systems. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 95, pp.54-61.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Two 4-year crop rotations with perennials (ley grass) in one of them, but only for one year. Ley system: spring barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> L.) – grass ley – winter wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.) – sugar beet (<i>Beta vulgaris</i> L.); ACC system: spring barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> L.), spring oil seed rape (<i>Brassica napus</i> L.), winter wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.) – sugar beet (<i>Beta vulgaris</i> L.).
Ali S A, Tedone L and Verdini L ; Mastro G De;. (2017). Effect of different crop management systems on rainfed durum wheat greenhouse gas emissions and carbon footprint under Mediterranean conditions. <i>Journal of cleaner production</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE only 5 years
Al-Kaisi M M. (2001). Impact of tillage and crop rotation systems on soil carbon sequestration. : agron.iastate.edu.	-Exclude on REVIEW No original data. data taken from: Hobbs, J. A. and P. A. Brown. 1965. Effects of cropping and management on nitrogen and organic contents of a western Kansas soil. <i>Tech. Bull. No. 144. Kansas Agric. Exp. Stn., Manhattan. Stauffer, R. S., R. Muckenhirn, and R. T. Odell. 1940. Organic carbon, pH, and aggregation of the soil of the Morrow plots as affected by type of cropping and manurial addition. J. Am. Soc. Agron. 32:819–832. Van Bavel, C. and F. Schaller. 1950. Soil aggregation, organic matter, and yields in a long-time experiment as affected by crop management. Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc. 15:399–408.</i>
Al-Kaisi M. (2008). Long-term Tillage and Crop Rotation Effect on Yield and Soil Carbon. : lib.dr.iastate.edu.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Less than 10 years
Al-Kaisi M M, Douelle A and Kwaw-Mensah D ;. (2014). Soil microaggregate and macroaggregate decay over time and soil carbon change as influenced by different tillage systems. <i>Journal of Soil and Water Conservation</i> , 69, pp.574-580.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study on corn (<i>Zea mays</i> L.)–soybean (<i>Glycine max</i> L.) rotations.
Al-Kaisi M M, Archontoulis S V; Kwaw-Mensah D and Miguez F ;. (2015). Tillage and Crop Rotation Effects on Corn Agronomic Response and Economic Return at Seven Iowa Locations. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 107, pp.1411-1424.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Reports yield only.
Almagro M and Martinez-Mena M . (2014). Litter decomposition rates of green manure as affected by soil erosion, transport and deposition processes, and the implications for the soil carbon balance of a rainfed olive grove under a dry Mediterranean climate. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 196, pp.167-177.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Almaz M G and Halim R A; Martini M Y; Samsuri A W;. (2017). Integrated Application of Poultry Manure and Chemical Fertiliser on Soil Chemical Properties and Nutrient Uptake of Maize and Soybean. <i>Malaysian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 21, pp.13-28.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Almeida D S and Penn C J; Rosolem C A;. (2018). Assessment of phosphorus availability in soil cultivated with ruzigrass. <i>Geoderma</i> , 312, pp.64-73.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Greenhouse study

Altieri MA and Nicholls Cl . (2017). The adaptation and mitigation potential of traditional agriculture in a changing climate. <i>Climatic Change</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW
Alvarez R. (2012). Soil organic carbon stock in pampean soils: changes associated to rotation and tillage. <i>Actas 19th ISTRO Conference</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Soil survey in the pampean region. Comparisons between Trees, uncropped, pasture, cropped, and flooded land.
Alvarez R, Steinbach H S and De Paepe ; J L ;. (2017). Cover crop effects on soils and subsequent crops in the pampas: A meta-analysis. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 170, pp.53-65.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Alvarez R, De Paepe and J L ;. (2019). Modelling the effects of stover harvest on soil organic carbon in the Pampas of Argentina. <i>Soil Research</i> , 57(3), pp.257-265.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Soybeans in all rotations
Amado T J. C, Bayer C and Conceição P C; Spagnollo E ; Costa De ; Campos ; B H ; Da Veiga ;. (2006). Potential of carbon accumulation in no-till soils with intensive use and cover crops in southern Brazil. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 35, pp.1599-1607.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION 1-year rotations only. Should be excluded.
Amato G, Ruisi P and Frenda A S; Di Miceli ; G ; Saia S ; Plaia A ; Giambalvo D ;. (2013). Long-Term Tillage and Crop Sequence Effects on Wheat Grain Yield and Quality. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 105, pp.1317-1327.	-Exclude on OUTCOME grain yield and grain protein only
Amiro B D, Tenuta M and Gervais M ; Glenn A J;. (2017). A decade of carbon flux measurements with annual and perennial crop rotations on the Canadian Prairies. <i>Agricultural and forest ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on OUTCOME perfect study, but only CO2 fluxes are measured. No soil samples what so ever!
Anderson-Teixeira K J, Masters M D; Black C K; Zeri M and Hussain M Z; Bernacchi C J; DeLucia E H;. (2013). Altered Belowground Carbon Cycling Following Land-Use Change to Perennial Bioenergy Crops. <i>Ecosystems</i> , 16, pp.508-520.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 4-year study
Ando K and Shinjo H . (2017). Slash-and-burn agriculture in Zambia. In: , ed., <i>Soils, Ecosystem Processes, and Agricultural Development: Tropical Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa.</i> ; , pp.253-274.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Arai M, Tayasu I and Komatsuzaki M ; Uchida M ; ;. (2013). Changes in soil aggregate carbon dynamics under no-tillage with respect to earthworm biomass revealed by radiocarbon analysis. <i>Soil and Tillage ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Shorter than 10 years
Arcand M M and Helgason B L; Lemke R L;. (2016). Microbial crop residue decomposition dynamics in organic and conventionally managed soils. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 107, pp.347-359.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Arenas-Lago D, Vega FA and Silva LFO ; Andrade ML ;. (2013). Soil interaction and fractionation of added cadmium in some Galician soils. <i>Microchemical Journal</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Arora VK, Boer GJ and Friedlingstein P ; Eby M ; ;. (2013). Carbon-concentration and carbon-climate feedbacks in CMIP5 Earth system models. <i>Journal of ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE -Exclude on INTERVENTION
Arrouays D, McKenzie N and Hempel J ; Forges AR de ;. (2014). <i>GlobalSoilMap: basis of the global spatial soil information system.</i> : books.google.com.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Book
Aschi A, Aubert M and Riah-Anglet W ; Nelieu S ; Dubois C ; Akpa-Vinceslas M ; Trinsoutrot-Gattin I ;. (2017). Introduction of Faba bean in crop rotation: Impacts on soil chemical and biological characteristics. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 120, pp.219-228.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study
Ashworth A J and Allen F L; Wight J P; Saxton A M; Tyler D D; Sams C E;. (2014). Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration Rates under Crop Sequence Diversity, Bio-Covers, and No-Tillage. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 78, pp.1726-1733.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 8-year study (2002-2009).
Ashworth A J and Allen F L; Wight J P; Saxton A M; Tyler D D;. (2014). Long-Term Soil Organic Carbon Changes as Affected by Crop Rotation and Bio-covers in No-Till Crop Systems. In: Hartemink A E and McSweeney K, ed., <i>Soil Carbon</i> . Dordrecht: Springer, pp.271-279.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 8-year study (2002-2009)
Ashworth A J and Allen F L; Saxton A M; Tyler D D;. (2016). Long-Term Corn Yield Impacted by Cropping Rotations and Bio-Covers under No-Tillage. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 108, pp.1495-1502.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Askari M S and Holden N M;. (2015). Quantitative soil quality indexing of temperate arable management systems. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 150, pp.57-67.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Assemien F L, Cantarel A A. M; Florio A and Lerondelle C ; Pommier T ; Gonnetty J T; Le Roux ; X ;. (2019). Different groups of nitrite-reducers and N2O-reducers have distinct ecological niches and functional roles in West African cultivated soils. <i>Soil Biology & Biochemistry</i> , 129, pp.39-47.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Assmann JM, Anghinoni I and Martins AP ; ;. (2014). Soil carbon and nitrogen stocks and fractions in a long-term integrated crop-livestock system under no-tillage in southern Brazil. <i>Agriculture and Ecosystems ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Grazing study in a pasture-soybean system
Astover A, Szajdak L W and Kölli R ;. (2016). Impact of long-term agricultural management and native forest ecosystem on the chemical and biochemical properties of retisols' organic matter. In: , ed., <i>Bioactive</i>	-Exclude on COMPARATOR One rotation only (potato, spring wheat, spring barley)

Compounds in Agricultural Soils. : Springer International Publishing, pp.149-171.	
Autret B, Mary B and Chenu C ; Balabane M ; Girardin C ; Bertrand M ; Grandeau G ; Beaudoin N ;. (2016). Alternative arable cropping systems: A key to increase soil organic carbon storage? Results from a 16 year field experiment. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 232, pp.150-164.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR No continuous crop, all rotations include legumes, different tillage in rotation with perennials.
Autret B, Beaudoin N and Rakotovololona L ; Bertrand M ; Grandeau G ; Grehan E ; Ferchaud F ; Mary B ;. (2019). Can alternative cropping systems mitigate nitrogen losses and improve GHG balance? Results from a 19-yr experiment in Northern France. <i>Geoderma</i> , 342, pp.20-33.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE They compare farming systems, so we can not compare the crop rotations
Averill C, Turner BL and Finzi AC ;. (2014). Mycorrhiza-mediated competition between plants and decomposers drives soil carbon storage. <i>Nature</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Awale R, Machado S and Rhinhart K ;. (2018). Soil Carbon, Nitrogen, pH, and Crop Yields in Winter Wheat-Spring Pea Systems. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 110(4), pp.1523-1531.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation (wheat-pea).
Aziz I, Mahmood T and Islam KR ;. (2013). Effect of long term no-till and conventional tillage practices on soil quality. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study (2002-2007)
Aziz I, Bangash N and Mahmood T ; Islam K R;. (2015). IMPACT OF NO-TILL AND CONVENTIONAL TILLAGE PRACTICES ON SOIL CHEMICAL PROPERTIES. <i>Pakistan Journal of Botany</i> , 47, pp.297-303.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Tillage and rotation study, but effects of rotations not reported.
Baah-Acheamfour M, Chang S X and Carlyle C N; Bork E W;. (2015). Carbon pool size and stability are affected by trees and grassland cover types within agroforestry systems of western Canada. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 213, pp.105-113.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Badger W B, Simmons A T; Murphy B W; Rawson A and Andersson K O; Lonergan V E;. (2014). The influence of land use and management on soil carbon levels for crop-pasture systems in Central New South Wales, Australia. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 196, pp.147-157.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR crop vs. pasture in crop-pasture rotations or permanent pasture
Bahr E, Zarogocin D C and Makeshin F ;. (2014). Soil nutrient stock dynamics and land-use management of annuals, perennials and pastures after slash-and-burn in the Southern Ecuadorian Andes. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 188, pp.275-288.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Bai SH, Blumfield TJ and Reverchon F ;. (2014). The impact of mulch type on soil organic carbon and nitrogen pools in a sloping site. <i>Biology and fertility of soils</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Baldock JA, Sanderman J and Macdonald LM ; Puccini A ;. (2014). Quantifying the allocation of soil organic carbon to biologically significant fractions. <i>Soil Research</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Bardhan S, Jose S and Udawatta R P; Fritsch F ;. (2013). Microbial community diversity in a 21-year-old temperate alley cropping system. <i>Agroforestry Systems</i> , 87, pp.1031-1041.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR maize (Zea mays)—soybean (Glycine max) rotation intercropped with trees but no comparator
Barel J M, Kuyper T W; Paul J and de Boer ; W ; Cornelissen J H. C; De Deyn ; G B ;. (2019). Winter cover crop legacy effects on litter decomposition act through litter quality and microbial community changes. <i>Journal of Applied Ecology</i> , 56(1), pp.132-143.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study
Barton L, Murphy DV and Butterbach-Bahl K ;. (2013). Influence of crop rotation and liming on greenhouse gas emissions from a semi-arid soil. <i>Agriculture and Ecosystems & ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study (2009-2010)
Basanta M and Alvarez C . (2015). Sustainable management of agricultural systems in the central region of Córdoba: Long-term experience in EEA INTA Manfredi. <i>Revista de Investigaciones Agropecuarias</i> , 41, pp.215-222.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Spanish
Bayer C, Mielniczuk J and Amado T J. C; Martin-Neto L ; Fernandes S V;. (2000). Organic matter storage in a sandy clay loam Acrisol affected by tillage and cropping systems in southern Brazil. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 54, pp.101-109.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION 1-year rotations only. Should be excluded.
Bayer C, Martin-Neto L and Mielniczuk J ; Ceretta C A;. (2000). Effect of no-till cropping systems on soil organic matter in a sandy clay loam Acrisol from Southern Brazil monitored by electron spin resonance and nuclear magnetic resonance. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 53, pp.95-104.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION 1-year rotations only. Should be excluded.
Bayer C, Gomes J and Zanatta J A; Vieira F C. B; Dieckow J ;. (2016). Mitigating greenhouse gas emissions from a subtropical Ultisol by using long-term no-tillage in combination with legume cover crops. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 161, pp.86-94.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-year cycles with winter cover crops only
Bedano J C, Vaquero F and Dominguez A ; Rodriguez M P; Wall L ; Lavelle P ;. (2019). Earthworms contribute to ecosystem process in no-till systems with high crop rotation intensity in Argentina. <i>Acta Oecologica-International Journal of Ecology</i> , 98, pp.14-24.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE The farms systems are different
Begueria S, Angulo-Martínez M and Gaspar L ; Navas A ;. (2015). Detachment of soil organic carbon by rainfall splash: Experimental assessment on three agricultural soils of Spain. <i>Geoderma</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk

Behrends Kraemer, F and Soria M A; Castiglioni M G; Duval M ; Galantini J ; Morrás H ;. (2017). Morpho-structural evaluation of various soils subjected to different use intensity under no-tillage. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 169, pp.124-137.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Soybean in all rotations
Bell TH, Yergeau E and Juck DF ; ;. (2013). Alteration of microbial community structure affects diesel biodegradation in an Arctic soil. <i>FEMS microbiology ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Beltran M J, Brutti L and Romaniuk R ; Bacigaluppo S ; Salvaggiotti F ; Sainz-Rozas H ; Galantini J A;. (2016). Soil organic matter quality, macro and micronutrient availability in response to the inclusion of wheat as cover crop. <i>Ciencia del Suelo</i> , 34, pp.67-79.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 6-year study
Benbi D K, Brar K and Toor A S; Sharma S ;. (2015). Sensitivity of Labile Soil Organic Carbon Pools to Long-Term Fertilizer, Straw and Manure Management in Rice-Wheat System. <i>Pedosphere</i> , 25, pp.534-545.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Berhongeray G, Alvarez R and Paepe J De; Caride C ; ;. (2013). Land use effects on soil carbon in the Argentine Pampas. <i>Geoderma</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Soil survey in the Pampas. Comparisons between trees, uncropped controls, seeded pastures, croppedfields and flooded lands. No detailed information on rotations.
Berthrong ST, Buckley DH and Drinkwater LE ;. (2013). Agricultural management and labile carbon additions affect soil microbial community structure and interact with carbon and nitrogen cycling. <i>Microbial ecology</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Multiple factors (crops and amendments) differ between the rotations. Also, there is little detail on the conventional rotation. What is meant by occasional legumes? Do we have any comparator here or do we just have two rotations with legumes (and no continuous monocultures and no rotation with perennials)?
Bhattarai M D, Secchi S and Schoof J ;. (2017). An Analysis of the Climate Change Mitigation Potential through Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration in a Corn Belt Watershed. <i>Environmental Management</i> , 59, pp.77-86.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Modelling study. Model validated using data from other studies (not reported here).
Bini D, Santos CA Dos and Bouillet JP ; ;. (2013). Eucalyptus grandis and Acacia mangium in monoculture and intercropped plantations: Evolution of soil and litter microbial and chemical attributes during early stages <i>Applied soil ecology</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Intercropping
Blanco-Canqui H, Shapiro C A and Wortmann C S; Drijber R A; Mamo M ; Shaver T M; Ferguson R B;. (2013). Soil organic carbon: The value to soil properties. <i>Journal of Soil and Water Conservation</i> , 68, pp.129A-134A.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Blanco-Canqui H, Gilley J E and Eisenhauer D E; Jasa P J; Boldt A ;. (2014). Soil Carbon Accumulation under Switchgrass Barriers. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 106, pp.2185-2192.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR crop rotation vs. permanent grass
Blanco-Canqui H, Francis C A and Galusha T D;. (2017). Does organic farming accumulate carbon in deeper soil profiles in the long term?. <i>Geoderma</i> , 288, pp.213-221.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR 4-year rotations including both legumes and perennials in all treatments.
Blesh J and Drinkwater LE . (2013). The impact of nitrogen source and crop rotation on nitrogen mass balances in the Mississippi River Basin. <i>Ecological Applications</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Blesh J and Drinkwater L E. (2014). Retention of N-15-Labeled Fertilizer in an Illinois Prairie Soil with Winter Rye. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 78, pp.496-508.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Boguzas V, Mikucioniene R and Slepeliene A ; Sinkeviciene A ; Feiza V ; Steponaviciene V ; Adamaviciene A ;. (2015). Long-term effect of tillage systems, straw and green manure combinations on soil organic matter. <i>Zemdirbyste-Agriculture</i> , 102, pp.243-250.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Identical rotations. Tillage and straw residue study.
Boincean B, Kassam A and Basch G ; Reicosky D ; Gonzalez E ; Reynolds T ; Ilusca M ; Cebotari M ; Rusnac G ; Cuzeac V ; Bulat L ; Pasat D ; Stadnic S ; Gavrilas S ; Boaghii I ;. (2016). Towards Conservation Agriculture systems in Moldova. <i>Aims Agriculture and Food</i> , 1, pp.369-386.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Boincean B and Francis C . (2017). Agroecological rotation designs reduce dependence on industrial inputs. <i>Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems</i> , 41(9-10), pp.1068-1080.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No soil C or OM data reported.
Bos J F. F. P, ten Berge and H F M; Verhagen J ; van Ittersum ; M K ;. (2016). Trade-offs in soil fertility management on arable farms. <i>Agricultural Systems</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR No continuous, leguminous, or perennial crop
Bos Jffp, ten Berge and H F M; Verhagen J ; van Ittersum ; M K ;. (2017). Trade-offs in soil fertility management on arable farms. <i>Agricultural Systems</i> , 157, pp.292-302.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Four rotations with winter wheat, potato, maize and sugar beet plus/minus mustard as cover crop
Bourguignon M, Archontoulis S and Moore K ; Lenssen A ;. (2017). A model for evaluating production and environmental performance of kenaf in rotation with conventional row crops. <i>Industrial Crops and Products</i> , 100, pp.218-227.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Modelling study, original carbon data not reported.
Bowles TM, Acosta-Martínez V and Calderón F ; ;. (2014). Soil enzyme activities, microbial communities, and carbon and nitrogen availability in	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE Tomato fields with vetch winter cover crops

organic agroecosystems across an intensively-managed agricultural landscape. <i>Soil Biology and ...</i> , pp..	
Brackinik R, Schmidt S and Walter D ; Bhuiyan S ; Buckley S ; Anderson J ;. (2017). Soil biological health-what is it and how can we improve it?. <i>International Sugar Journal</i> , 119(1426), pp.806-814.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Bradford MA, Keiser AD and Davies CA ; Mersmann CA ;. (2013). Empirical evidence that soil carbon formation from plant inputs is positively related to microbial growth. <i>Biogeochemistry</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Brandão M and Canals LM i. (2013). Global characterisation factors to assess land use impacts on biotic production. <i>The International Journal of Life Cycle ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW
Brovkin V, Boysen L and Arora VK ; Boisier JP ;. (2013). Effect of anthropogenic land-use and land-cover changes on climate and land carbon storage in CMIP5 projections for the twenty-first century. <i>Journal of ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Bu R Y, Lu J W; Ren T and Liu B ; Li X K; Cong R H;. (2015). Particulate Organic Matter Affects Soil Nitrogen Mineralization under Two Crop Rotation Systems. <i>Plos One</i> , 10, pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwb
Butterbach-Bahl K, Baggs EM and ;. (2013). Nitrous oxide emissions from rsts: how well do we understand the processes and their controls?. : rstb.royalsocietypublishing.org .	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Büchi L, Wendling M and Amossé C ; Jeangros B ;. (2017). Long and short term changes in crop yield and soil properties induced by the reduction of soil tillage in a long term experiment in Switzerland. <i>Soil and Tillage ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation - no comparator
Calegari A, Tourdonnet S and Tessier D ; Rheinheimer D S; Ralisch R ; Hargrove W ; Guimaraes M F; Filho J T;. (2013). Influence of Soil Management and Crop Rotation on Physical Properties in a Long-Term Experiment in Parana, Brazil. <i>Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis</i> , 44, pp.2019-2031.	-Exclude on OUTCOME C not reported for differnt rotations (but for different tillage).
Capriel P. (2013). Trends in organic carbon and nitrogen contents in agricultural soils in Bavaria (south Germany) between 1986 and 2007. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 64, pp.445-454.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Region-wide Soil survey, not appropriate for answering our question.
Cardinael R, Chevallier T and Cambou A ; Beral C ; Barthes B G; Dupraz C ; Durand C ; Kouakoua E ; Chenu C ;. (2017). Increased soil organic carbon stocks under agroforestry: A survey of six different sites in France. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 236, pp.243-255.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Agroforestry study. Different crop rotations at different sites. Not sure if comparable.
Carolan R and Fornara D A. (2016). Soil carbon cycling and storage along a chronosequence of re-seeded grasslands: Do soil carbon stocks increase with grassland age?. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 218, pp.126-132.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Permanent grasslands only
Carter M R, Noronha C and Peters R D; Kimpinski J ;. (2009). Influence of conservation tillage and crop rotation on the resilience of an intensive long-term potato cropping system: Restoration of soil biological properties after the potato phase. <i>Agriculture and Ecosystems and Environment</i> , 133, pp.32-39.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR SOC results for the 3-year rotation only. No comparator.
Carvalho A M, Marchao R L; Bustamante M M. D; de Alcantara and F A ; Coser T R;. (2014). Characterization of cover crops by NMR spectroscopy: impacts on soil carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus under tillage regimes. <i>Revista Ciencia Agronomica</i> , 45, pp.968-975.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Cattaneo F, Di Gennaro and P ; Barbanti L ; Giovannini C ; Labra M ; Moreno B ; Benitez E ; Marzadori C ;. (2014). Perennial energy cropping systems affect soil enzyme activities and bacterial community structure in a South European agricultural area. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 84, pp.213-222.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Corg measured but not reported for different rotations. Focus on enzymes.
Cattaneo F, Barbanti L and Gioacchini P ; Ciavatta C ; Marzadori C ;. (2014). C-13 abundance shows effective soil carbon sequestration in Miscanthus and giant reed compared to arable crops under Mediterranean climate. <i>Biology and Fertility of Soils</i> , 50, pp.1121-1128.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 9-year study
Cavigelli M A and Mirsky S B; Teasdale J R; Spargo J T; Doran J. (2013). Organic grain cropping systems to enhance ecosystem services. <i>Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems</i> , 28, pp.145-159.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Cazorla C R and Cisneros J M; Moreno I S; Galarza C M;. (2017). Soil carbon and aggregate stability improvement by fertilization and cover crops. <i>Ciencia del Suelo</i> , 35(2), pp.301-313.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Spanish
Celik I, Günal H and Acar M ; Gök M ; Barut Z B;. (2017). Long-term tillage and residue management effect on soil compaction and nitrate leaching in a Typic Haploxerert soil. : researchgate.net .	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation (winter wheat (Triticum aestivum L.)-corn (Zea Mays L.) and wheatsoybean (Glycine max. L.)).
Chambers A, Lal R and Paustian K ;. (2016). Soil carbon sequestration potential of US croplands and grasslands: Implementing the 4 per Thousand Initiative. <i>Journal of Soil and Water Conservation</i> , 71, pp.68A-74A.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Chan K Y, Conyers M K; Li G D; Helyar K R; Poile G and Oates A ; Barchia I M;. (2011). Soil carbon dynamics under different cropping and pasture	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Hard to find comparable rotations with no

management in temperate Australia: Results of three long-term experiments. <i>Soil Research</i> , 49, pp.320-328.	confounders (stubble management, tillage). Values predicted rather than measured.
Chang J F, Ciais P and Viovy N ; Vuichard N ; Sultan B ; Soussana J F;. (2015). The greenhouse gas balance of European grasslands. <i>Global Change Biology</i> , 21, pp.3748-3761.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Continental scale modelling of GHG balances on grasslands.
Chaopricha NT and Marín-Spiotta E . (2014). Soil burial contributes to deep soil organic carbon storage. <i>Soil Biology and Biochemistry</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Chaplot V and Cooper M . (2015). Soil aggregate stability to predict organic carbon outputs from soils. <i>Geoderma</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Chapman S J, Bell J S; Campbell C D; Hudson G and Lilly A ; Nolan A J; Robertson A H. J; Potts J M; Towers W ;. (2013). Comparison of soil carbon stocks in Scottish soils between 1978 and 2009. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 64, pp.455-465.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Soil survey, no detailed info on rotations.
Chappell A, Baldock J and Rossel RV ;. (2013). Sampling soil organic carbon to detect change over time. : apo.org.au .	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Very interesting paper on sampling strategy.
Chaudhury S, Bhattacharyya T and Wani S P; Pal D K; Sahrawat K L; Nimje A ; Chandran P ; Venugopalan M V; Telpande B ;. (2016). Land use and cropping effects on carbon in black soils of semi-arid tropical India. <i>Current Science</i> , 110, pp.1692-1698.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Various locations in India. Different rotations at different sites, not necessarily comparable.
Chen Z, Yu G and Ge J ; Sun X ; Hirano T ; Saigusa N ; ;. (2013). Temperature and precipitation control of the spatial variation of terrestrial ecosystem carbon exchange in the Asian region. <i>Agricultural and Forest ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Regional modelling study
Chen S, Xu C M and Yan J X; Zhang X G; Zhang X F; Wang D Y;. (2016). The influence of the type of crop residue on soil organic carbon fractions: An 11-year field study of rice-based cropping systems in southeast China. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 223, pp.261-269.	-Exclude on SOIL TYPE
Chimento C and Amaducci S . (2015). Characterization of fine root system and potential contribution to soil organic carbon of six perennial bioenergy crops. <i>Biomass & Bioenergy</i> , 83, pp.116-122.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Choudhary M, Jat H S and Datta A ; Yadav A K; Sapkota T B; Mondal S ; Meena R P; Sharma P C; Jat M L;. (2018). Sustainable intensification influences soil quality, biota, and productivity in cereal-based agroecosystems. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 126, pp.189-198.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Choudhury SG, Srivastava S and Singh R ; ;. (2014). Tillage and residue management effects on soil aggregation, organic carbon dynamics and yield attribute in rice–wheat cropping system under reclaimed sodic soil. <i>Soil and Tillage ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Christiansen S, Ryan J and Singh M ; Ates S ; Bahhady F ; Mohamed K ; Youssef O ; Loss S ;. (2015). Potential legume alternatives to fallow and wheat monoculture for Mediterranean environments. <i>Crop & Pasture Science</i> , 66, pp.113-121.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Chu B, Zaid F and Eivazi F ;. (2016). Long-Term Effects of Different Cropping Systems on Selected Enzyme Activities. <i>Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis</i> , 47, pp.720-730.	-Exclude on SOIL TYPE
Cogger C G and Bary A I; Kennedy A C; Fortuna A M;. (2013). Long-Term Crop and Soil Response to Biosolids Applications in Dryland Wheat. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 42, pp.1872-1880.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Cogger C G and Bary A I; Myhre E A; Fortuna A M; Collins D P;. (2016). Soil Physical Properties, Nitrogen, and Crop Yield in Organic Vegetable Production Systems. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 108, pp.1142-1154.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE <10 yr (2015-2012)
Comeau L P and Lemke R L; Knight J D; Bedard-Haughn A. (2013). Carbon input from C-13-labeled crops in four soil organic matter fractions. <i>Biology and Fertility of Soils</i> , 49, pp.1179-1188.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Greenhouse study
Conceicao P C, Dieckow J and Bayer C ;. (2013). Combined role of no-tillage and cropping systems in soil carbon stocks and stabilization. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 129, pp.40-47.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-yr rotations with intercropping only
Conceição P C, Dieckow J and Bayer C ;. (2013). Combined role of no-tillage and cropping systems in soil carbon stocks and stabilization. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 129, pp.40-47.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-year rotations only
Cong W W and Ren T S; Li B G;. (2015). Assessing the Impact of Afforestation on Soil Organic C Sequestration by Means of Sequential Density Fractionation. <i>Plos One</i> , 10, pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Congreves K A, Smith J M; Nemeth D D; Hooker D C; Van Eerd and L L ;. (2014). Soil organic carbon and land use: Processes and potential in Ontario's long-term agro-ecosystem research sites. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 94, pp.317-336.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Cook R L and Trlica A. (2016). Tillage and Fertilizer Effects on Crop Yield and Soil Properties over 45 Years in Southern Illinois. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 108, pp.415-426.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage and fertilizer experiment, corn-soybean rotation
Cordova E M, Chirinda N and Li F ; Olesen J E;. (2018). Contributions from carbon and nitrogen in roots to closing the yield gap between conventional and organic cropping systems. <i>Soil Use and Management</i> , 34(3), pp.335-342.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Legumes in all rotations. No continuous crop and no perennial component.

Cotching W E, Oliver G and Downie M ; Corkrey R ; Doyle R B;. (2013). Land use and management influences on surface soil organic carbon in Tasmania. <i>Soil Research</i> , 51, pp.615-630.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Soil survey
Cotrufo MF, Wallenstein MD and Boot CM ;. (2013). The Microbial Efficiency-Matrix Stabilization (MEMS) framework integrates plant litter decomposition with soil organic matter stabilization: do labile plant inputs form stable soil organic matter?. <i>Global Change ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Cui J F and Askari M S; Holden N M;. (2014). Relating Soil Carbon and Soil Structure to Land Use Management. In: Hartemink A E and McSweeney K, ed., <i>Soil Carbon</i> . Dordrecht: Springer, pp.297-304.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Cui J F and Askari M S; Holden N M;. (2015). Grassland soil carbon and nitrogen stocks under temperate livestock grazing. <i>Soil Research</i> , 53, pp.485-493.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Culman S W and Snapp S S; Green J M; Gentry L E;. (2013). Short- and Long-Term Labile Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Dynamics Reflect Management and Predict Corn Agronomic Performance. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 105, pp.493-502.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE < 10 yr (2008-2011)
da Silva , F D and Amado T J. C; Ferreira A D; Assmann J M; Anghinoni I ; Carvalho P C. D;. (2014). Soil carbon indices as affected by 10 years of integrated crop-livestock production with different pasture grazing intensities in Southern Brazil. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 190, pp.60-69.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Rye grass + Black oat - soy bean, no comparator
Dahmardeh M and Hodiani A . (2016). Assessment of soil elements in intercropping based on mathematical modelling. <i>Computers and Electronics in Agriculture</i> , 122, pp.218-224.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Bwh
Daigh A L, Sauer T and Xiao X H; Horton R ;. (2015). Comparison of Models for Determining Soil-Surface Carbon Dioxide Effluxes in Different Agricultural Systems. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 107, pp.1077-1086.	-Exclude on OUTCOME CO2 fluxes only, soil C not reported.
Dal Ferro, N and Cocco E ; Lazzaro B ; Berti A ; Morari F ;. (2016). Assessing the role of agri-environmental measures to enhance the environment in the Veneto Region, Italy, with a model-based approach. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 232, pp.312-325.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Regional modelling study, no detailed info on rotations.
Dalal R C and Thornton C M; Cowie B A;. (2013). Turnover of organic carbon and nitrogen in soil assessed from delta C-13 and delta N-15 changes under pasture and cropping practices and estimates of greenhouse gas emissions. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 465, pp.26-35.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Cropped vs pasture
Dalal R C and Strong W M; Weston E J; Cooper J E; Lehane K J; King A J;. (2018). Farming systems' productivity and soil organic carbon stocks following fertilisers, no-tillage or legumes on a fertility-depleted soil in a semi-arid subtropical region. <i>Soil Research</i> , 56(4), pp.429-440.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Data not possible to use
Dalias P and Neocleous D . (2017). Comparative Analysis of the Nitrogen Effect of Common Agricultural Practices and Rotation Systems in a Rainfed Mediterranean Environment. <i>Plants-Basel</i> , 6(4), pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 8-year study
Dalzell B J, Johnson J M. F; Tallaksen J and Allan D L; Barbour N W;. (2013). Simulated Impacts of Crop Residue Removal and Tillage on Soil Organic Matter Maintenance. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 77, pp.1349-1356.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE < 10 years
Das B, Chakraborty D and Singh VK ; Aggarwal P ; ;. (2014). Effect of integrated nutrient management practice on soil aggregate properties, its stability and aggregate-associated carbon content in an intensive rice-wheat system. <i>Soil and Tillage ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Das A, Layek J and Ramkrushna G I; Patel D P; Choudhury B U; Krishnappa R ; Buragohain J ; Yadav G S;. (2018). Modified system of rice intensification for higher crop and water productivity in Meghalaya, India: opportunities for improving livelihoods for resource-poor farmers. <i>Paddy and Water Environment</i> , 16(1), pp.23-34.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwb
Davinic M, Moore-Kucera J and Acosta-Martinez V ; Zak J ; Allen V ;. (2013). Soil fungal distribution and functionality as affected by grazing and vegetation components of integrated crop-livestock agroecosystems. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 66, pp.61-70.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Bsk
de Andrade Barbosa, M and de Sousa Ferraz ; R L ; Coutinho E L. M; Coutinho Neto ; A M ; da Silva ; M S ; Fernandes C ; Rigobelo E C;. (2019). Multivariate analysis and modeling of soil quality indicators in long-term management systems. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 657, pp.457-465.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
de Araújo Santos, G A and Moitinho M R; de Oliveira Silva ; B ; Xavier C V; Teixeira D D. B; Corá J E; Júnior N L. S;. (2019). Effects of long-term no-tillage systems with different succession cropping strategies on the variation of soil CO2 emission. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 686, pp.413-424.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
de Figueiredo , C C and de Oliveira ; A D ; dos Santos ; I L ; Ferreira E A. B; Malaquias J V; de Sa ; M A C; de Carvalho ; A M ; dos Santos ; J D D;. (2018). Relationships between soil organic matter pools and nitrous oxide emissions of agroecosystems in the Brazilian Cerrado. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 618, pp.1572-1582.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw

De Leon-Gonzalez , F and Fuentes-Ponce M H; Bautista-Cruz A ; Leyva-Pablo T ; Castillo-Juarez H ; Rodriguez-Sanchez L M;. (2018). Cactus crop as an option to reduce soil C-CO2 emissions in soils with declining fertility. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i> , 38(1), pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwb
De Mastro , F and Brunetti G ; Traversa A ; Coccozza C ;. (2019). Effect of crop rotation, fertilisation and tillage on main soil properties and its water extractable organic matter. <i>Soil Research</i> , 57(4), pp.365-373.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation
de Medeiros , E V and Notaro K D; de Barros ; J A ; Moraes W D; Silva A O; Moreira K A;. (2015). Absolute and specific enzymatic activities of sandy entisol from tropical dry forest, monoculture and intercropping areas. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 145, pp.208-215.	-Exclude on CLIMATE As & BSh
de Sant-Anna , S A C and Jantalia C P; Sá J M; Vilela L ; Marchão R L; Alves B J. R; Urquiaga S ; Boddey R M;. (2016). Changes in soil organic carbon during 22 years of pastures, cropping or integrated crop/livestock systems in the Brazilian Cerrado. <i>Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems</i> , , pp.1-20.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
de Souza , G P and de Figueiredo ; C C ; de Sousa ; D M G;. (2016). Soil organic matter as affected by management systems, phosphate fertilization, and cover crops. <i>Pesquisa Agropecuaria Brasileira</i> , 51, pp.1668-1676.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
de Souza , G P and de Figueiredo ; C C ; de Sousa ; D M G;. (2016). Relationships between labile soil organic carbon fractions under different soil management systems. <i>Scientia Agricola</i> , 73, pp.535-542.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
de Valenca , A W and Vanek S J; Meza K ; Ccanto R ; Olivera E ; Scurrah M ; Lantinga E A; Fonte S J;. (2017). Land use as a driver of soil fertility and biodiversity across an agricultural landscape in the Central Peruvian Andes. <i>Ecol Appl</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Soil survey, different rotations in different locations not necessarily comparable.
de Vries , F T and Thebault E ; Liiri M ; Birkhofer K ; Tsiafouli M A; Bjornlund L ; Jorgensen H B; Brady M V; Christensen S ; de Ruiter ; P C ; d'Hertefeldt T ; Frouz J ; Hedlund K ; Hemerik L ; Hol W H. G; Hotes S ; Mortimer S R; Setälä H ; Sgardelis S P; Uteseny K ; van der Putten ; W H ; Wolters V ; Bardgett R D;. (2013). Soil food web properties explain ecosystem services across European land use systems. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America</i> , 110, pp.14296-14301.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study, no detailed information on rotations.
de Wit , M P and Lesschen J P; Londo M H. M; Faaij A P. C;. (2014). Greenhouse gas mitigation effects of integrating biomass production into European agriculture. <i>Biofuels Bioproducts & Biorefining-Biofpr</i> , 8, pp.374-390.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
DeHaan L R and Ismail B P;. (2017). Perennial cereals provide ecosystem benefits. : researchgate.net.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE No experiment reported
Delays LA Milesi, Irizar AB and Andriulo AE ; ;. (2013). Effect of continuous agriculture of grassland soils of the Argentine rolling pampa on soil organic carbon and nitrogen. ... and <i>Environmental Soil ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study using data collected from different sites for each rotation.
Deng L, Wang K B and Li J P; Shangguan Z P; Sweeney S ;. (2014). Carbon Storage Dynamics in Alfalfa (<i>Medicago sativa</i>) Fields in the Hilly-Gully Region of the Loess Plateau, China. <i>Clean-Soil Air Water</i> , 42, pp.1253-1262.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwb
Devi M, King Solomon and E ; Nivas D ; Chandru S ;. (2013). Enhancement of soil fertility through agro inputs on response to cover crop of <i>Crotalaria juncea</i> L. In: , ed., <i>Microbiological Research in Agroecosystem Management</i> . : Springer India, pp.175-186.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Di Bene , C and Marchetti A ; Francaviglia R ; Farina R ;. (2016). Soil organic carbon dynamics in typical durum wheat-based crop rotations of Southern Italy. <i>Italian Journal of Agronomy</i> , 11, pp.209-216.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study
Dick M, da Silva and M A ; Dewes H ;. (2015). Mitigation of environmental impacts of beef cattle production in southern Brazil - Evaluation using farm-based life cycle assessment. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 87, pp.58-67.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Dijkstra FA, Carrillo Y and Pendall E ; ;. (2014). Rhizosphere priming: a nutrient perspective. ... <i>Microbial Regulation of ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Dimassi B, Cohan JP and Labreuche J ; Mary B ;. (2013). Changes in soil carbon and nitrogen following tillage conversion in a long-term experiment in Northern France. <i>Agriculture and ecosystems & ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study
Ding H Y, Ali A and Cheng Z H;. (2018). Dynamics of a Soil Fungal Community in a Three-Year Green Garlic/Cucumber Crop Rotation System in Northwest China. <i>Sustainability</i> , 10(5), pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Pot-based 3-year study (2012-2015).
Diochon A, Gregorich E G and Kellman L ; Morrison M ; Ma B L;. (2016). Greater soil C inputs accelerate loss of C in cropping systems with low N input. <i>Plant and Soil</i> , 400, pp.93-105.	-Exclude on OUTCOME C from maize (C4) only reported for different rotations.
Doltra J, Olesen J E and Baez D ; Louro A ; Chirinda N ;. (2015). Modeling nitrous oxide emissions from organic and conventional cereal-based cropping systems under different management, soil and climate factors. <i>European Journal of Agronomy</i> , 66, pp.8-20.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Dondini M, Richards M and Pogson M ; Jones E O; Rowe R L; Keith A M; McNamara N P; Smith J U; Smith P ;. (2016). Evaluation of the ECOSSE model for simulating soil organic carbon under <i>Miscanthus</i> and short	-Exclude on INTERVENTION No relevant crop rotations.

rotation coppice-willow crops in Britain. <i>Global Change Biology Bioenergy</i> , 8, pp.790-804.	
Donigian A S, Jr and Patwardhan A S; Jackson R B. Iv; Barnwell T O; Jr ; Weinrich K B; Rowell A L;. (2018). Modeling the impacts of agricultural management practices on soil carbon in the central U.S. In: , ed., <i>Soil Management and Greenhouse Effect. :</i> , pp.121-136.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
dos Santos, D C and Farias M D; de Lima ; C L R; Kunde R J; Pillon C N; Flores C A;. (2013). Physical and chemical fractionation of organic matter of an Alfisol under different use systems. <i>Ciencia Rural</i> , 43, pp.838-844.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study
Dou F G and Hons F M; Ocumpaugh W R; Read J C; Hussey M A; Muir J P;. (2013). Soil Organic Carbon Pools Under Switchgrass Grown as a Bioenergy Crop Compared to Other Conventional Crops. <i>Pedosphere</i> , 23, pp.409-416.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Rotations can be compared to permanent grass only.
Dou F G and Hons F M; Ocumpaugh W R; Read J C; Hussey M A; Muir J P;. (2013). Soil Organic Carbon Pools Under Switchgrass Grown as a Bioenergy Crop Compared to Other Conventional Crops. <i>Pedosphere</i> , 23, pp.409-416.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Switchgrass and kleingrass only 9 years. Bermudagrass compared with conventionally tilled rotations.
Dou X L, Xu X and Shu X ; Zhang Q F; Cheng X L;. (2016). Shifts in soil organic carbon and nitrogen dynamics for afforestation in central China. <i>Ecological Engineering</i> , 87, pp.263-270.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation (rape and peanut).
Dou X, Cheng X and He P ; Zhu P ; Zhou W ; Wang L ;. (2017). Dynamics of physically- separated soil organic carbon pools assessed from $\delta^{13}C$ changes under 25 years of cropping systems. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 174, pp.6-13.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwa
Dou X, Li F and Cheng X ; Zhu P ;. (2018). Soil organic carbon and nitrogen dynamics induced by continuous maize cropping compared to maize-soya bean rotation. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 69(3), pp.535-544.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwa
Drewniak B A, Mishra U and Song J ; Prell J ; Kotamarthi V R;. (2015). Modeling the impact of agricultural land use and management on US carbon budgets. <i>Biogeosciences</i> , 12, pp.2119-2129.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Droppelmann K J and Snapp S S; Waddington S R;. (2017). Sustainable intensification options for smallholder maize-based farming systems in sub-Saharan Africa. <i>Food Security</i> , 9(1), pp.133-150.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No soil C or OM data reported.
Dufosse K, Drewer J and Gabrielle B ; Drouet J L;. (2014). Effects of a 20-year old <i>Miscanthus x giganteus</i> stand and its removal on soil characteristics and greenhouse gas emissions. <i>Biomass & Bioenergy</i> , 69, pp.198-210.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Comparison between a 20-year old <i>Miscanthus</i> stand and a rotation of annual crops.
Dunn JB, Mueller S and Kwon H ; ;. (2013). Land-use change and greenhouse gas emissions from corn and cellulosic ethanol. : <i>biotechnologyforbiofuels</i>	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Duval BD, Anderson-Teixeira KJ and Davis SC ; Keogh C ; ;. (2013). Predicting greenhouse gas emissions and soil carbon from changing pasture to an energy crop. : <i>journals.plos.org</i> .	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Pasture vs energy cane (<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> L.)
Duval Matias Ezequiel, De Sa Pereira and Eduardo ; Iglesias Julio Osvaldo; Galantini Juan Alberto;. (2014). EFECTO DE USO Y MĀNEJO DEL SUELO SOBRE LAS FRACCIONES DE CARBONO ORGĀNICO EN UN ARGIUDDL. EFFECT OF SOIL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON ORGANIC CARBON FRACTIONS IN AN ARGIUDDL., 32, pp.105-115.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study
Duval M E and Galantini J A; MartĀnez J M; Iglesias J O;. (2016). Comparison between agricultural and natural quality indices based on organic carbon. <i>Ciencia del Suelo</i> , 34, pp.197-209.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Spanish
Duval M E and Galantini J A; MartĀnez J M; Limbozzi F. (2018). Labile soil organic carbon for assessing soil quality: influence of management practices and edaphic conditions. <i>Catena</i> , 171, pp.316-326.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Not possible to compare rotations at individual sites.
Eclesia R P, Jobbagy E G; Jackson R B; Rizzotto M and Pineiro G ;. (2016). Stabilization of new carbon inputs rather than old carbon decomposition determines soil organic carbon shifts following woody or herbaceous vegetation transitions. <i>Plant and Soil</i> , 409, pp.99-116.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Emmel C, Winkler A and Hortnagl L ; Revall A ; Ammann C ; D'Odorico P ; Buchmann N ; Eugster W ;. (2018). Integrated management of a Swiss cropland is not sufficient to preserve its soil carbon pool in the long term. <i>Biogeosciences</i> , 15(17), pp.5377-5393.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation.
Ernst O R, Dogliotti S and Cadenazzi M ; Kemanian A R;. (2018). Shifting crop-pasture rotations to no-till annual cropping reduces soil quality and wheat yield. <i>Field Crops Research</i> , 217, pp.180-187.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Continuous cropping after pasture, not possible to compare crop rotations.
Fan J, Ding W and Xiang J ; Qin S ; Zhang J ; Ziadi N ;. (2014). Carbon sequestration in an intensively cultivated sandy loam soil in the North China Plain as affected by compost and inorganic fertilizer application. <i>Geoderma</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Fan F, Henriksen C B and Porter J ;. (2018). Relationship between stoichiometry and ecosystem services: A case study of it organic farming systems. <i>Ecological Indicators</i> , 85, pp.400-408.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION

Farina R, Coleman K and Whitmore A P; (2013). Modification of the RothC model for simulations of soil organic C dynamics in dryland regions. <i>Geoderma</i> , 200, pp.18-30.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study using data extracted from other studies
Farina R, Marchetti A and Francaviglia R ; Napoli R ; Di Bene ; C ;. (2017). Modeling regional soil C stocks and CO2 emissions under Mediterranean cropping systems and soil types. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 238, pp.128-141.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Feng W, Plante AF and Six J ;. (2013). Improving estimates of maximal organic carbon stabilization by fine soil particles. <i>Biogeochemistry</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Fernandez R, Frasier I and Noellemeyer E ; Quiroga A ;. (2017). Soil quality and productivity under zero tillage and grazing on Mollisols in Argentina - A long-term study. <i>Geoderma Regional</i> , 11, pp.44-52.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation: sunflower (<i>Helianthus annuus</i> L.), wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.), oats (<i>Avena sativa</i> L.), corn (<i>Zea mays</i> L.), 4 years of alfalfa (<i>Medicago sativa</i> L.) and tall fescue (<i>Festuca arundinacea</i> (Schreb.) Darbysh. = <i>Schedonorus arundinaceus</i> (Schreb.) Dumort) pasture, soybean (<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.), and winter cover crops (<i>Secale cereale</i> , <i>Vicia villosa</i> Roth.).
Ferrari A E, Ravnskov S and Wall L G;. (2018). Crop rotation in no-till soils modifies the soil fatty acids signature. <i>Soil Use and Management</i> , 34(3), pp.427-436.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No soil C or OM data reported
Ferre C, Comolli R and Leip A ; Seufert G ;. (2014). Forest conversion to poplar plantation in a Lombardy floodplain (Italy): effects on soil organic carbon stock. <i>Biogeosciences</i> , 11, pp.6483-6493.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Natural forest vs poplar plantation
Ferreira A D and Amado T J. C; Nicoloso R D; Sa J C. D; Fiorin J E; Hansel D S. S; Menefee D. (2013). Soil carbon stratification affected by long-term tillage and cropping systems in southern Brazil. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 133, pp.65-74.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Ferreira E A. B, Bustamante M M. D; Resck D V. S; de Figueiredo and C C ; Pinto A D; Malaquias J V;. (2016). Carbon Stocks in Compartments of Soil Organic Matter 31 Years after Substitution of Native Cerrado Vegetation by Agroecosystems. <i>Revista Brasileira De Ciencia Do Solo</i> , 40, pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Ferreira A D, Amado T and Ric C W; Diaz D A. R; Keller C ; Inagaki T M;. (2016). Can no-till grain production restore soil organic carbon to levels natural grass in a subtropical Oxisol?. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 229, pp.13-20.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR leguminous plants in all rotations, no continuous crop, no perennial crop.
Ferreira A D, Sa J C. D; Lal R and Tivet F ; Briedis C ; Inagaki T M; Goncalves D R. P; Romaniw J ;. (2018). Macroaggregation and soil organic carbon restoration in a highly weathered Brazilian Oxisol after two decades under no-till. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 621, pp.1559-1567.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Two similar rotations, both involving legumes, no perennials.
Oliveira Ferreira A D, Amado T J. C; Rice C W; Diaz D A. R; Briedis C and Inagaki T M; Goncalves D R. P;. (2018). Driving factors of soil carbon accumulation in Oxisols in long-term-no-till systems of South Brazil. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 622, pp.735-742.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No C or OM data reported, No relevant comparator
Finzi AC, Abramoff RZ and Spiller KS ;. (2015). Rhizosphere processes are quantitatively important components of terrestrial carbon and nutrient cycles. <i>Global change ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW
Fornara DA, Banin L and Crawley MJ ;. (2013). Multi-nutrient vs. nitrogen-only effects on carbon sequestration in grassland soils. <i>Global Change Biology</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Forte A, Fagnano M and Fierro A ;. (2017). Potential role of compost and green manure amendment to mitigate soil GHGs emissions in Mediterranean drip irrigated maize production systems. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 192, pp.68-78.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No soil C or OM data reported.
Francioni M, D'ottavio P and Lai R ; Trozzo L ; Budimir K ; Foresi L ; Kishimoto-Mo A W; Baldoni N ; Allegranza M ; Tessei G ; Toderi M ;. (2019). Seasonal soil respiration dynamics and carbon-stock variations in mountain permanent grasslands compared to arable lands. <i>Agriculture (Switzerland)</i> , 9(8), pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Lentil and emmer rotations only, compared with permanent grassland.
Franco A L. C, Cherubin M R; Pavinato P S; Cerri C E. P; Six J and Davies C A; Cerri C C;. (2015). Soil carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus changes under sugarcane expansion in Brazil. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 515, pp.30-38.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Fu B, Wang S and Su C ; Forsius M ;. (2013). Linking ecosystem processes and ecosystem services. <i>Current Opinion in Environmental ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Fu X, Wang J and Sainju U M; Liu W Z;. (2017). Soil Carbon Fractions in Response to Long-Term Crop Rotations in the Loess Plateau of China. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 81(3), pp.503-513.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Fuchslueger L, Bahn M and Fritz K ; Hasibeder R ;. (2014). Experimental drought reduces the transfer of recently fixed plant carbon to soil microbes and alters the bacterial community composition in a mountain : Wiley Online Library.	-Exclude on CLIMATE ET
Fultz L M, Moore-Kucera J and Zobeck T M; Acosta-Martinez V ; Wester D B; Allen V G;. (2013). Organic carbon dynamics and soil stability in five	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk

semiarid agroecosystems. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 181, pp.231-240.	
Fultz L M, Moore-Kucera J and Zobeck T M; Acosta-Martinez V ; Allen V G;. (2013). Aggregate Carbon Pools after 13 Years of Integrated Crop-Livestock Management in Semiarid Soils. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 77, pp.1659-1666.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Fultz L M, Moore-Kucera J and Calderon F ; Acosta-Martinez V ;. (2014). Using Fourier-Transform Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy to Distinguish Soil Organic Matter Composition Dynamics in Aggregate Fractions of Two Agroecosystems. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 78, pp.1940-1948.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Gamble J D, Feyerreisen G W; Papiernik S K; Wentz C and Baker J ;. (2017). Regression-kriged soil organic carbon stock changes in manured corn silage-alfalfa production systems. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 81(6), pp.1557-1566.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Not replicated (but pseudo-replicated).
Gamble J D, Feyerreisen G W; Papiernik S K; Wentz C and Baker J ;. (2017). Erratum: Regression-Kriged Soil Organic Carbon Stock Changes in Manured Corn Silage–Alfalfa Production Systems (<i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i>) DOI: 10.2136/sssaj2017.04.0138. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 82(4), pp.1013.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Gan Y T, Campbell C A; Jansen H H; Lemke R and Liu L P;. (2009). Carbon input to soil by oilseed and pulse crops in semiarid environment. <i>Agric Ecosyst Environ</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study
Garcia-Gonzalez I, Hontoria C and Gabriel J L; Alonso-Ayuso M ; Quemada M ;. (2018). Cover crops to mitigate soil degradation and enhance soil functionality in irrigated land. <i>Geoderma</i> , 322, pp.81-88.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Gaudin A C. M, Janovicek K and Deen B ; Hooker D C;. (2015). Wheat improves nitrogen use efficiency of maize and soybean-based cropping systems. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 210, pp.1-10.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Yields reported, soil C not reported.
Gelfand I, Sahajpal R and Zhang X S; Izaurrealde R C; Gross K L; Robertson G P;. (2013). Sustainable bioenergy production from marginal lands in the US Midwest. <i>Nature</i> , 493, pp.514-+.	-Exclude on OUTCOME GHG emissions only
George S, Wright D L and Marois J J;. (2013). Impact of grazing on soil properties and cotton yield in an integrated crop-livestock system. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 132, pp.47-55.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Grazing study with only one rotation.
Georgiadis P, Vesterdal L and Stupak I ; Raulund-Rasmussen K ;. (2017). Accumulation of soil organic carbon after cropland conversion to short-rotation willow and poplar. <i>GCB Bioenergy</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Cropland vs SRWC. Rotations on cropland not defined.
Ghaley B B and Sandhu H S; Porter J R;. (2015). Relationship between C:N/C:O stoichiometry and ecosystem services in managed production systems. <i>PLoS ONE</i> , 10, pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Intercropping vs monocropping
Ghimire R, Machado S and Rhinhart K ;. (2015). Long-Term Crop Residue and Nitrogen Management Effects on Soil Profile Carbon and Nitrogen in Wheat-Fallow Systems. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 107, pp.2230-2240.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION winter wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.)–summer fallow (WW–SF) system only
Ghimire R, Thapa V R and Cano A ; Acosta-Martinez V ;. (2019). Soil organic matter and microbial community responses to semiarid croplands and grasslands management. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 141, pp.30-37.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Ghosh P K, Hazra K K; Venkatesh M S; Nath C P; Singh J and Nadarajan N ;. (2019). Increasing Soil Organic Carbon Through Crop Diversification in Cereal–Cereal Rotations of Indo-Gangetic Plain. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences India Section B - Biological Sciences</i> , 89(2), pp.429-440.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSH
Githinji L. (2014). Effect of biochar application rate on soil physical and hydraulic properties of a sandy loam. <i>Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Gol C and Yilmaz H . (2017). The effect of land use type / land cover and aspect on soil properties at the gokdere catchment in northwestern turkey. <i>Sumarski List</i> , 141(9-10), pp.459-468.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Land-use study, crop rotations not recorded.
Gollany H T and Fortuna A M; Samuel M K; Young F L; Pan W L; Pecharko M. (2013). Soil Organic Carbon Accretion vs. Sequestration Using Physicochemical Fractionation and CQESTR Simulation. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 77, pp.618-629.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 7-year study
Gonzalez J M. (2018). Runoff and losses of nutrients and herbicides under long-term conservation practices (no-till and crop rotation) in the U.S. Midwest: A variable intensity simulated rainfall approach. <i>International Soil and Water Conservation Research</i> , 6(4), pp.265-274.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE No variability reported, not clear wich rotation is present in plots.
Gonzalez-Prieto S, Diaz-Ravina M and Martin A ; Lopez-Fando C ;. (2013). Effects of agricultural management on chemical and biochemical properties of a semiarid soil from central Spain. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 134, pp.49-55.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study on chickpea/barley rotation
Gos P, Loucougaray G and Colace M P; Arnoldi C ; Gaucherand S ; Dumazel D ; Girard L ; Delorme S ; Lavorel S ;. (2016). Relative contribution of soil, management and traits to co-variations of multiple ecosystem properties in grasslands. <i>Oecologia</i> , 180, pp.1001-1013.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION

Grandy A and Robertson G . (2007). Land-Use Intensity Effects on Soil Organic Carbon Accumulation Rates and Mechanisms. <i>Ecosystems</i> , 10, pp.59-74.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Comparator is perennial grass.
Gregory A S, Dungait J A. J; Watts C W; Bol R and Dixon E R; White R P; Whitmore A P;. (2016). Long-term management changes topsoil and subsoil organic carbon and nitrogen dynamics in a temperate agricultural system. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 67, pp.421-430.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION No crop rotation
Griffiths B S, Rombke J and Schmelz R M; Scheffczyk A ; Faber J H; Bloem J ; Peres G ; Cluzeau D ; Chabbi A ; Suhadolc M ; Sousa J P; da Silva ; P M ; Carvalho F ; Mendes S ; Morais P ; Francisco R ; Pereira C ; Bonkowski M ; Geisen S ; Bardgett R D; de Vries ; F T ; Bolger T ; Dirilgen T ; Schmidt O ; Winding A ; Hendriksen N B; Johansen A ; Philippot L ; Plassart P ; Bru D ; Thomson B ; Griffiths R I; Bailey M J; Keith A ; Rutgers M ; Mulder C ; Hannula S E; Creamer R ; Stone D ;;. (2016). Selecting cost effective and policy-relevant biological indicators for European monitoring of soil biodiversity and ecosystem function. <i>Ecological Indicators</i> , 69, pp.213-223.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Groenigen KJ Van, Qi X and Osenberg CW ; Luo Y ;;. (2014). Faster decomposition under increased atmospheric CO2 limits soil carbon storage., pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Guareschi R F, Pereira M G; Soares P F. C; Banos F D; Perin A and Rossi C Q;. (2018). Compartments of organic matter in an Oxisol under different types of no-tillage systems. <i>Semina-Ciencias Agrarias</i> , 39(2), pp.533-548.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Gubler A, Wächter D and Schwab P ; Müller M ; Keller A ;;. (2019). Twenty-five years of observations of soil organic carbon in Swiss croplands showing stability overall but with some divergent trends. <i>Environmental Monitoring and Assessment</i> , 191(5), pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Large-scale survey study.
Guedes O, Blanco-Canqui H and da Silva ; A P ;;. (2013). Least limiting water range of the soil seedbed for long-term tillage and cropping systems in the central Great Plains, USA. <i>Geoderma</i> , 207, pp.99-110.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Guidi P, Antisari L V and Mare B T ; Vianello G ; Falsone G ;;. (2017). Effects of Alfalfa on Aggregate Stability, Aggregate Preserved-C and Nutrients in Region Mountain Agricultural Soils 1 Year After its Planting. <i>Land Degradation & Development</i> , 28(8), pp.2408-2417.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 1-year study of only one rotation (wheat,peas,barley,cllover)
Guimarães DV, Gonzaga MIS and Silva TO da ;;. (2013). Soil organic matter pools and carbon fractions in soil under different land uses. <i>Soil and Tillage ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE As
Hamel C, Gan Y and Messer D ; Bainard L D;. (2019). Soil 16S DNA sequence data and corresponding soil property and wheat yield data from a 72-plot field experiment involving pulses and wheat crops grown in rotations in the semiarid prairie. Data in Brief, 23, pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Only 4 years
Handlířové M, Procházková B and Smutný V ;;. (2016). Yields of selected catch crops in dry conditions. <i>Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis</i> , 64, pp.1139-1148.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Catch crop study on winter wheat – catch crop – spring barley rotations
Hanegraaf M C, Hoffland E and Kuikman P J; Brussaard L ;;. (2009). Trends in soil organic matter contents in Dutch grasslands and maize fields on sandy soils. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 60, pp.213-222.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Large scale soil survey study.
Hansen E M and Munkholm L J; Olesen J E; Melander B. (2015). Nitrate Leaching, Yields and Carbon Sequestration after Noninversion Tillage, Catch Crops, and Straw Retention. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 44, pp.868-881.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Intervention duration <10 years.
Hao Y J and Wang Y H; Chang Q R; Wei X R;. (2017). Effects of Long-Term Fertilization on Soil Organic Carbon and Nitrogen in a Highland Agroecosystem. <i>Pedosphere</i> , 27(4), pp.725-736.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Hao X X and You M Y; Han X Z; Li H B; Zou W X; Xing B S;. (2017). Redistribution of Different Organic Carbon Fractions in the Soil Profile of a Typical Chinese Mollisol with Land-Use Change. <i>Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis</i> , 48(20), pp.2369-2380.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwb
Hasson A, Wiley T and Woolston G ;;. (2013). Whole soil sampling to compare carbon sequestration under perennial pastures of western Australia. <i>Nature Environment and Pollution Technology</i> , 12, pp.203-208.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Annuals vs. permanent grass. Also < 10 yr.
Havstad L T. (2014). Cover crop stubble and straw management in seed production of timothy (<i>Phleum pratense</i> L.), meadow fescue (<i>Festuca pratensis</i> Huds.), and red clover (<i>Trifolium pratense</i> L.). <i>Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica Section B-Soil and Plant Science</i> , 64, pp.547-557.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Cover crop study
Hawes C, Alexander C J and Begg G S; Iannetta P P. M; Karley A J; Squire G R; Young M ;;. (2018). Plant Responses to an Integrated Cropping System Designed to Maintain Yield Whilst Enhancing Soil Properties and Biodiversity. <i>Agronomy-Basel</i> , 8(10), pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study, reported C data not possible to use, only one rotation (no comparator)?
Hawkins J, Weersink A and Wagner-Riddle C ; Fox G ;;. (2015). Optimizing ration formulation as a strategy for greenhouse gas mitigation in intensive dairy production systems. <i>Agricultural Systems</i> , 137, pp.1-11.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Hazra K K, Ghosh P K; Venkatesh M S; Nath C P; Kumar N and Singh M ; Singh J ; Nadarajan N ;;. (2018). Improving soil organic carbon pools through inclusion of summer mungbean in cereal-cereal cropping systems in Indo-	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh

Gangetic plain. Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science, 64(12), pp.1690-1704.	
Hazra K K, Nath C P; Singh U and Praharaj C S; Kumar N ; Singh S S; Singh N P;. (2019). Diversification of maize-wheat cropping system with legumes and integrated nutrient management increases soil aggregation and carbon sequestration. Geoderma, 353, pp.308-319.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
He Y, Xu M and Qi Y ; Dong Y ; He X ; Li J ; Liu X ; Sun L ;. (2017). Differential responses of soil microbial community to four-decade long grazing and cultivation in a semi-arid grassland. Sustainability (Switzerland), 9(1), pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE
He Y T and Xu M G; Qi Y C; Dong Y S; He X H; Li J W; Liu X C; Sun L J;. (2017). Differential Responses of Soil Microbial Community to Four-Decade Long Grazing and Cultivation in a Semi-Arid Grassland. Sustainability, 9, pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Mongolia
Heikkinen J, Ketoja E and Nuutinen V ; ;. (2013). Declining trend of carbon in Finnish cropland soils in 1974–2009. Global change ..., , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Nationwide soil survey
Henderson B B, Gerber P J; Hilinski T E; Falcucci A and Ojima D S; Salvatore M ; Conant R T;. (2015). Greenhouse gas mitigation potential of the world's grazing lands: Modeling soil carbon and nitrogen fluxes of mitigation practices. Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment, 207, pp.91-100.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Hengl T, Jesus JM de and MacMillan RA ; Batjes NH ; ;. (2014). SoilGrids1km—global soil information based on automated mapping. : journals.plos.org.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE soil survey
Hidalgo C, Merino A and Osorio-Hernández V ; Etchevers J D; Figueroa B ; Limon A ; Aguirre E ;. (2019). Physical and chemical processes determining soil organic matter dynamics in a managed vertisol in a tropical dryland area. Soil and Tillage Research, 194, pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Higashi T, Yunghui M and Komatsuzaki M ; Miura S ; Hirata T ; Araki H ; Kaneko N ; Ohta H ;. (2014). Tillage and cover crop species affect soil organic carbon in Andosol, Kanto, Japan. Soil & Tillage Research, 138, pp.64-72.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE Winter cover crop study
Hirsch P R, Jhurrea D and Williams J K; Murray P J; Scott T ; Misselbrook T H; Goulding K W. T; Clark I M;. (2017). Soil resilience and recovery: rapid community responses to management changes. Plant and Soil, 412(1-2), pp.283-297.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study (2008-2012).
Hlavinka P, Trnka M and Kersebaum K C; Čermák P ; Pohanková E ; Orság M ; Pokorný E ; Fischer M ; Brtnický M ; Žalud Z ;. (2014). Modelling of yields and soil nitrogen dynamics for crop rotations by HERMES under different climate and soil conditions in the Czech Republic. Journal of Agricultural Science, 152, pp.188-204.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Holman J D, Arnet K and Dille J ; Maxwell S ;. (2018). Can cover or forage crops replace fallow in the semiarid Central Great Plains?. Crop ..., , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Hossain M Z, Rezaul Karim and Md ; Majumder B R; Akter F ;. (2019). Microbial and enzymatic activity as influenced by existing cropping pattern in the soils of Ganges floodplain. Plant Science Today, 6(3), pp.309-314.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Hoyle F C, D'Antuono M and Overheu T ; Murphy D V;. (2013). Capacity for increasing soil organic carbon stocks in dryland agricultural systems. Soil Research, 51, pp.657-667.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Crop rotation with pasture and livestock.
Hu B, Zhou M H and Dannenmann M ; Saiz G ; Simon J ; Bilela S ; Liu X P; Hou L ; Chen H ; Zhang S X; Butterbach-Bahl K ; Rennenberg H ;. (2017). Comparison of nitrogen nutrition and soil carbon status of afforested stands established in degraded soil of the Loess Plateau, China. Forest Ecology and Management, 389, pp.46-58.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION No crop rotation.
Hu T, Sorensen P and Olesen J E;. (2018). Soil carbon varies between different organic and conventional management schemes in arable agriculture. European Journal of Agronomy, 94, pp.79-88.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Legumes in all rotations. No continuous crop and no perennial component.
Huang J X, Chen Y Q; Pan J and Liu W R; Yang G L; Xiao X P; Zheng H B; Tang W G; Tang H M; Zhou L J;. (2019). Carbon footprint of different agricultural systems in China estimated by different evaluation metrics. Journal of Cleaner Production, 225, pp.939-948.	-Exclude on SOIL TYPE
Hulugalle N R and Weaver T B; Finlay L A; Heimoana V. (2013). Soil organic carbon concentrations and storage in irrigated cotton cropping systems sown on permanent beds in a Vertisol with restricted subsoil drainage. Crop & Pasture Science, 64, pp.799-805.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Bsh according to authors. Also only 9 years (2002-2011).
Hulugalle N R, Strong C and McPherson K ; Nachimuthu G ;. (2017). Carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus stoichiometric ratios under cotton cropping systems in Australian Vertisols: a meta-analysis of seven experiments. Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems, , pp.1-11.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh, BSk, BWh
Hurisso T T and Norton J B; Norton U. (2013). Soil profile carbon and nitrogen in prairie, perennial grass-legume mixture and wheat-fallow production in the central High Plains, USA. Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment, 181, pp.179-187.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Hurisso T T and Norton J B; Norton U. (2014). Labile soil organic carbon and nitrogen within a gradient of dryland agricultural land-use intensity in Wyoming, USA. Geoderma, 226, pp.1-7.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study on wheat–fallow rotations

Hurisso T T and Norton J B; Mukhwana E J; Norton U. (2015). Soil Organic Carbon and Nitrogen Fractions and Sugar Beet Sucrose Yield in Furrow-Irrigated Agroecosystems. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 79, pp.876-888.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Idowu O J and Kircher P. (2016). Soil quality of semi-arid conservation reserve program lands in Eastern New Mexico. <i>Arid Land Research and Management</i> , 30, pp.153-165.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Zhang D B, Yao Z Y; Chen J and Yao P W; Zhao N ; He W X; Li Y Y; Zhang S Q; Zhai B N; Wang Z H; Huang D L; Cao W D; Gao Y J;. (2019). Improving soil aggregation, aggregate-associated C and N, and enzyme activities by green manure crops in the Loess Plateau of China. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Irizar A, Andriulo A and Mary B ;. (2013). Long-term impact of no tillage in two intensified crop rotations on different soil organic matter fractions in Argentine rolling Pampa. <i>Open Agriculture Journal</i> , 7, pp.22-31.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only two rotations, both with legumes (maize-wheat/soybean and maize-soybean). No other comparator
Ito T, Araki M and Higashi T ; Komatsuzaki M ; Kaneko N ; Ohta H ;. (2015). Responses of soil nematode community structure to soil carbon changes due to different tillage and cover crop management practices over a nine-year period in Kanto, Japan. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> , 89, pp.50-58.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION tillage-, cover crop-, and manure study
Jacobs A, Jungert S and Koch H J;. (2015). Soil organic carbon as affected by direct drilling and mulching in sugar beet - wheat rotations. <i>Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science</i> , 61, pp.1079-1087.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Just one rotation (mustard-sugar beet-winter wheat)
Jafarian Z and Kaviani A . (2013). Effects of land-use change on soil organic carbon and nitrogen. <i>Communications in soil science and plant ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Jain N K and Jat R S; Meena H N; Chakraborty K. (2018). Productivity, Nutrient, and Soil Enzymes Influenced with Conservation Agriculture Practices in Peanut. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 110(3), pp.1165-1172.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Jandl G, Acksel A and Baum C ; Leinweber P ;. (2015). Indicators for soil organic matter quality in no-till soils under perennial crops in Central Sweden. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 148, pp.74-84.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION SRC (with willows) vs meadow (with grass).
Janz B, Weller S and Kraus D ; Racela H S; Wassmann R ; Butterbach-Bahl K ; Kiese R ;. (2019). Greenhouse gas footprint of diversifying rice cropping systems: Impacts of water regime and organic amendments. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 270, pp.41-54.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Am
Jarvis N, Koestel J and Messing I ;;. (2013). Influence of soil, land use and climatic factors on the hydraulic conductivity of soil. <i>Hydrology and Earth ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW
Jat H S, Datta Ashim and Sharma P C; Kumar Virender ; Yadav A K; Choudhary Madhu ; Choudhary Vishu ; Gathala M K; Sharma D K; Jat M L; Yaduvanshi N P. S; Singh Gurbachan ; McDonald A ;. (2018). Assessing soil properties and nutrient availability under conservation agriculture practices in a reclaimed sodic soil in cereal-based systems of North-West India. <i>Archiv Fur Acker- Und Pflanzenbau Und Bodenkunde</i> , 64(4), pp.531-45.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Jat S L, Parihar C M; Dey A and Nayak H S; Ghosh A ; Pariha N ; Goswami A K; Singh A K;. (2019). Dynamics and temperature sensitivity of soil organic carbon mineralization under medium-term conservation agriculture as affected by residue and nitrogen management options. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 190, pp.175-185.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study of two rotations, both including legumes
Jat H S, Datta A and Choudhary M ; Yadav A K; Choudhary V ; Sharma P C; Gathala M K; Jat M L; McDonald A ;. (2019). Effects of tillage, crop establishment and diversification on soil organic carbon, aggregation, aggregate associated carbon and productivity in cereal systems of semi-arid Northwest India. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 190, pp.128-138.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Jemai I, Ben Aissa and N ; Ben Guirat ; S ; Ben-Hammouda M ; Gallali T ;. (2013). Impact of three and seven years of no-tillage on the soil water storage, in the plant root zone, under a dry subhumid Tunisian climate. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 126, pp.26-33.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study
Jian Y, Zeng G J and Zhou P ; Yuan H Z; Ge T D; Zou D S; Wu J S;. (2014). Input and distribution of autotrophic microbe-assimilated carbon in humus and aggregate fractions of soils. <i>Research of Environmental Sciences</i> , 27, pp.1499-1504.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Chinese
Joensuu K and Saarinen M . (2016). Applying soil quality indicators in the context of life cycle assessment in a Finnish case study. <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , , pp.1-15.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Johnson J M. F, Novak J M; Varvel G E; Stott D E; Osborne S L; Karlen D L; Lamb J A; Baker J and Adler P R;. (2014). Crop Residue Mass Needed to Maintain Soil Organic Carbon Levels: Can It Be Determined?. <i>Bioenergy Research</i> , 7, pp.481-490.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Johnson J M. F and Barbour N W;. (2016). Nitrous Oxide Emission and Soil Carbon Sequestration from Herbaceous Perennial Biofuel Feedstocks. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 80, pp.1057-1070.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Comparator is permanent grass.

Jones C D and Oates L G; Robertson G P; Izaurralde R C;. (2018). Perennialization and Cover Cropping Mitigate Soil Carbon Loss from Residue Harvesting. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 47(4), pp.710-717.	-Exclude on REVIEW Check refs in table 1.
Kahlon M S, Lal R and Ann-Varughese M ;. (2013). Twenty two years of tillage and mulching impacts on soil physical characteristics and carbon sequestration in Central Ohio. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 126, pp.151-158.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Karaca Siyami, Gülser Füsün and Selçuk Ramazan ;. (2018). Relationships between soil properties, topography and land use in the Van Lake Basin, Turkey. <i>Eurasian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 7(2), pp.115-120.	-Exclude on OUTCOME nothing about length of study and no variance measures (and nothing about replicates)
Karlen D L and Stott D E; Cambardella C A; Kremer R J; King K W; McCarty G W;. (2014). Surface soil quality in five midwestern cropland Conservation Effects Assessment Project watersheds. <i>Journal of Soil and Water Conservation</i> , 69, pp.393-401.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Sampling in a large number of sites, intervention duration not reported but probably variable.
Karunaratne SB, Bishop TFA and Baldock JA ; Odeh IOA ;. (2014). Catchment scale mapping of measureable soil organic carbon fractions. <i>Geoderma</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Kasper M, Freyer B and Hulsbergen K J; Schmid H ; Friedel J K;. (2015). Humus balances of different farm production systems in main production areas in Austria. <i>Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science</i> , 178, pp.25-34.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Kátaí J, Döring T and Tállai M ; Balla-Kovács A ; Henzsel I ; Makádi M ; Sándor Z ; Vágó I ;. (2018). Influence of alternative plant nutrition methods on soil microbial characteristics in long-term experiments. <i>Agrokémia és Talajtan</i> , 67(1), pp.79-90.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-year rotations only
Katterer T, Andersson L and Andren O ; Persson J ;. (2008). Long-term impact of chronosequential land use change on soil carbon stocks on a Swedish farm. <i>Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems</i> , 81, pp.145-155.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Comparator is permanent grass.
Katterer T, Roobroeck D and Andren O ; Kimutai G ; Karlun E ; Kirchmann H ; Nyberg G ; Vanlauwe B ; de Nowina ; K R ;. (2019). Biochar addition persistently increased soil fertility and yields in maize-soybean rotations over 10 years in sub-humid regions of Kenya. <i>Field Crops Research</i> , 235, pp.18-26.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Af/Aw, 1-year maize-soybean rotation
Kauer K, Astover A and Viiralt R ; Raave H ; Kätterer T ;. (2019). Evolution of soil organic carbon in a carbonaceous glacial till as an effect of crop and fertility management over 50 years in a field experiment. <i>Agriculture and Ecosystems and Environment</i> , 283, pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION No crop rotation.
Kazula M J and Lauer J G;. (2018). The influence of crop rotation on corn total biomass production. <i>Journal of Soil and Water Conservation</i> , 73(5), pp.541-548.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No SOC data for the different rotations
Keith A M, Rowe R L; Parmar K and Perks M P; Mackie E ; Dondini M ; McNamara N P;. (2015). Implications of land-use change to Short Rotation Forestry in Great Britain for soil and biomass carbon. <i>Global Change Biology Bioenergy</i> , 7, pp.541-552.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR SRF vs grass or arable. no detailed info on rotations.
Khalil M I, Kiely G and O'Brien P ; Muller C ;. (2013). Organic carbon stocks in agricultural soils in Ireland using combined empirical and GIS approaches. <i>Geoderma</i> , 193, pp.222-235.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Khanal S, Anex R P and Gelder B K; Wolter C ;. (2014). Nitrogen balance in Iowa and the implications of corn-stover harvesting. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 183, pp.21-30.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Kiani M, Hernandez-Ramirez G and Quideau S ; Smith E ; Janzen H ; Larney F J; Puurveen D ;. (2017). Quantifying sensitive soil quality indicators across contrasting long-term land management systems: Crop rotations and nutrient regimes. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 248, pp.123-135.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No variation measures! Else the perfect study
Kibet L C, Blanco-Canqui H and Mitchell R B; Schacht W H;. (2016). Root biomass and soil carbon response to growing perennial grasses for bioenergy. <i>Energy Sustainability and Society</i> , 6, pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION grass monoculture vs mixture
Kibet L C, Blanco-Canqui H and Jasa P ;. (2016). Long-term tillage impacts on soil organic matter components and related properties on a Typic Argiudoll. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 155, pp.78-84.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study
Kibunja C N and Mwaura F B; Mugendi D N; Gicheru P T; Wamungo J W; Bationo A. (2012). Strategies for maintenance and improvement of soil productivity under continuous maize and beans cropping system in the sub-humid highlands of Kenya: Case study of the long-term trial at kabete. In: , ed., <i>Lessons learned from Long-term Soil Fertility Management Experiments in Africa</i> . : Springer Netherlands, pp.59-84.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation (1 yr maize-bean)
King A E and Hofmockel K S;. (2017). Diversified cropping systems support greater microbial cycling and retention of carbon and nitrogen. <i>Agriculture and Ecosystems and Environment</i> , 240, pp.66-76.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Legumes in all rotations, no continuous cropping, no perennials
King A E and Blesh J. (2018). Crop rotations for increased soil carbon: perennality as a guiding principle. <i>Ecological Applications</i> , 28(1), pp.249-261.	-Exclude on REVIEW Men bör läses og skal med i diskussion
Kirkby CA, Richardson AE and Wade LJ ; ;. (2014). Nutrient availability limits carbon sequestration in arable soils. <i>Soil Biology and ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION

Kismanyoky T and Toth Z. (2013). Effect of mineral and organic fertilization on soil organic carbon content as well as on grain production of cereals in the IOSDV (ILTE) long-term field experiment, Keszthely, Hungary. Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science, 59, pp.1121-1132.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Fertilization study in a 3-year cereal crop rotation (maize, winter wheat, winter barley) system.
Knebl L, Leithold G and Schulz F ; Brock C ;. (2017). The role of soil depth in the evaluation of management-induced effects on soil organic matter. European Journal of Soil Science, 68(6), pp.979-987.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR All rotations involve legumes, no perennials.
Kome C E and Andrews S S; Franzluebbers A J;. (2013). Soil organic carbon assessment using the Carbon Management Evaluation Tool for Voluntary Reporting and the Soil Conditioning Index. Journal of Soil and Water Conservation, 68, pp.296-305.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study, no observed SOC data reported.
Kowalenko C G and Ihnat M. (2013). Residual effects of combinations of limestone, zinc and manganese applications on soil and plant nutrients under mild and wet climatic conditions. Canadian Journal of Soil Science, 93, pp.113-125.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Kramer S, Marhan S and Haslwimmer H ; Russ L ; ;. (2013). Temporal variation in surface and subsoil abundance and function of the soil microbial community in an arable soil. Soil Biology and ..., , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Krauss M, Perrochet F and Lori M ; Ruser R ; Muller T ; Zikeli S ; Gruber S ; Claupein W ; Mader P ; Gattinger A ;. (2017). Reduced tillage in organic farming - climate aspects. Agrarforschung Schweiz, 8(6), pp.226-231.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Kravchenko Y S, Chen Q and Liu X ; Herbert S J; Zhang X ;. (2016). Conservation Practices and Management in Ukrainian Mollisols. Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology, 18, pp.845-854.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only rotations with both perennials and legumes.
Kumar V, Rawat A K and Rao D L. N;. (2018). Slow and fast-growing soybean rhizobial population, their symbiotic efficiency and soil nitrogen behavior under different cropping systems in Vertisols of Madhya Pradesh, India. Legume Research, 41(4), pp.617-623.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Different rotations on different locations.
Kumar A, Mishra V N and Biswas A K; Somasundaram J ;. (2018). Soil organic carbon, dehydrogenase activity and fluorescein diacetate as influenced by contrasting tillage and cropping systems in Vertisols of Central India. Journal of Environmental Biology, 39(6), pp.1047-1053.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study (2011-2014)
Lacoste M, Minasny B and McBratney A ; Michot D ; Viaud V ; ;. (2014). High resolution 3D mapping of soil organic carbon in a heterogeneous agricultural landscape. Geoderma, , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Ladoni M, Basir A and Robertson P G; Kravchenko A N;. (2016). Scaling-up: cover crops differentially influence soil carbon in agricultural fields with diverse topography. Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment, 225, pp.93-103.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR corn-soybean-wheat rotations only
Lal R. (2015). Sequestering carbon and increasing productivity by conservation agriculture. Journal of Soil and Water Conservation, , pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW
Lalani B, Aleter B and Kassam S N; Bapoo A ; Kassam A ;. (2018). Potential for Conservation Agriculture in the Dry Marginal Zone of Central Syria: A Preliminary Assessment. Sustainability, 10(2), pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study (2010-2012), not replicated, Climate BSK.
Lam SK, Chen D and Norton R ; Armstrong R ;. (2013). The effect of elevated atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration on the contribution of residual legume and fertilizer nitrogen to a subsequent wheat crop. Plant and soil, , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Lamb M C and Sorensen R B; Butts C L;. (2018). Crop response to biochar under differing irrigation levels in the southeastern USA. Journal of Crop Improvement, 32(3), pp.305-317.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study (2010-2013), no soil C or OM data reported.
Lammel D R, Butterbach-Bahl K and Cerri C E. P; Louis S ; Schnitzler J P; Feigl B J; Cerri C C;. (2017). C and N stocks are not impacted by land use change from Brazilian Savanna (Cerrado) to agriculture despite changes in soil fertility and microbial abundances. Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science, 180(4), pp.436-445.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Latati M, Aouiche A and Tellah S ; Laribi A ; Benlahrech S ; Kaci G ; Ouarem F ; Ounane S M;. (2017). Intercropping maize and common bean enhances microbial carbon and nitrogen availability in low phosphorus soil under Mediterranean conditions. European Journal of Soil Biology, 80, pp.9-18.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE
Lazicki P A, Liebman M and Wander M M;. (2016). Root Parameters Show How Management Alters Resource Distribution and Soil Quality in Conventional and Low-Input Cropping Systems in Central Iowa. Plos One, 11, pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Legumes in all rotations, no continuous cropping, no perennials
Lee J and Archer D W. (2014). Simulating soil carbon change in oilseed cropping system in North Dakota. In : : American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers, pp.286-293. Available at: function URL() { [native code] }.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Observed data from one rotation only
Lehman R M and Osborne S L; Duke S E;. (2017). Diversified No-Till Crop Rotation Reduces Nitrous Oxide Emissions, Increases Soybean Yields, and Promotes Soil Carbon Accrual. Soil Science Society of America Journal, 81(1), pp.76-83.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Both rotations (a 2-yr corn-soybean rotation and a 4-yr corn-field peas-winter wheat-soybean rotation) involve legumes, no perennials.
Lehmann A, Zheng W and Rillig M C;. (2017). Soil biota contributions to soil aggregation. Nature ecology & evolution, , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Review not related to crop rotation

Leifeld J, Angers DA and Chenu C ; ;. (2013). Organic farming gives no climate change benefit through soil carbon sequestration. <i>Proceedings of the ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Lensen A W and Sainju U M; Jabro J D; Iversen W M; Allen B L; Evans R G; (2014). Crop Diversification, Tillage, and Management System Influence Spring Wheat Yield and Water Use. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 106, pp.1445-1454.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Soil C in any form not reported
Leon E, Vargas R and Bullock S ; Lopez E ; ;. (2014). Hot spots, hot moments, and spatio-temporal controls on soil CO 2 efflux in a water-limited ecosystem. <i>Soil Biology and ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Lewandowski I. (2013). Soil carbon and biofuels: Multifunctionality of ecosystem services. In: , ed., <i>Ecosystem Services and Carbon Sequestration in the Biosphere.</i> : Springer Netherlands, pp.333-356.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Li J, Wang G and Allison SD ; Mayes MA ; Luo Y ;. (2014). Soil carbon sensitivity to temperature and carbon use efficiency compared across microbial-ecosystem models of varying complexity. <i>Biogeochemistry</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Li H, Wang L G and Qiu J J; Li C S; Gao M F; Gao C Y;. (2014). Calibration of DNDC model for nitrate leaching from an intensively cultivated region of Northern China. <i>Geoderma</i> , 223, pp.108-118.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Li D J, Liu J and Chen H ; Zheng L ; Wen L ; Wang K L;. (2018). Forage grass cultivation increases soil organic carbon and nitrogen pools in a karst region, southwest China. <i>Land Degradation & Development</i> , 29(12), pp.4397-4404.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-year maize-soybean rotation
Li D J, Liu J and Chen H ; Zheng L ; Wang K L;. (2018). Soil gross nitrogen transformations in responses to land use conversion in a subtropical karst region. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 212, pp.1-7.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Li D J, Liu J and Chen H ; Zheng L ; Wang K L;. (2018). Soil microbial community responses to forage grass cultivation in degraded karst soils, Southwest China. <i>Land Degradation & Development</i> , 29(12), pp.4262-4270.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Liang D, Sun F and Wattiaux M A; Cabrera V E; Hedtcke J L; Silva E M;. (2017). Effect of feeding strategies and cropping systems on greenhouse gas emission from Wisconsin certified organic dairy farms. <i>Journal of Dairy Science</i> , 100(7), pp.5957-5973.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Multiple farm survey
Liebig M A and Hendrickson J R;. (2010). Response of soil carbon and nitrogen to transplanted alfalfa in North Dakota rangeland. <i>Canadian journal of soil ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Liu CA, Li FR and Zhou LM ; Feng Q ; Li X ; Pan CC ; ;. (2013). Effects of water management with plastic film in a semi-arid agricultural system on available soil carbon fractions. <i>European journal of soil ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Bsk
Liu E, Teclerariam SG and Yan C ; Yu J ; Gu R ; Liu S ; He W ; ;. (2014). Long-term effects of no-tillage management practice on soil organic carbon and its fractions in the northern China. <i>Geoderma</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwb
Liu Y, Tian F P and Jia P Y; Zhang J G; Hou F J; Wu G L;. (2017). Leguminous species sequester more carbon than gramineous species in cultivated grasslands of a semi-arid area. <i>Solid Earth</i> , 8, pp.83-91.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Liu C Y, Yao Z S; Wang K and Zheng X H; Li B G;. (2019). Net ecosystem carbon and greenhouse gas budgets in fiber and cereal cropping systems. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 647, pp.895-904.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-year rotation
Lopez-Bellido R J, Muñoz-Romero V and Fuentes-Guerra R ; Fernandez-Garcia P ; Lopez-Bellido L ;. (2017). No-till: A key tool for sequestering C and N in microaggregates on a Mediterranean Vertisol. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 166, pp.131-137.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No SOC data for individual rotations (just significance of rotation). Data could perhaps be requested from authors?
López-Santiago J G, Casanova-Lugo F and Villanueva-López G ; Díaz-Echeverría V F; Solorio-Sánchez F J; Martínez-Zurimendi P ; Aryal D R; Chay-Canul A J;. (2019). Carbon storage in a silvopastoral system compared to that in a deciduous dry forest in Michoacán, Mexico. <i>Agroforestry Systems</i> , 93(1), pp.199-211.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Lorenz K and Lal R . (2014). Biochar application to soil for climate change mitigation by soil organic carbon sequestration. <i>Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW Not about crop rotation
Loss A, Pereira M G and Costa E M; Beutler S J; Piccolo M C;. (2016). Soil fertility, humic fractions and natural abundance of 13C y 15N in soil under different land use in Paraná State, Southern Brazil. <i>Idesia</i> , 34, pp.27-38.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION tillage
Lu W W, Ding W X; Zhang J H; Li Y and Luo J F; Bolan N ; Xie Z B;. (2014). Biochar suppressed the decomposition of organic carbon in a cultivated sandy loam soil: A negative priming effect. <i>Soil Biology & Biochemistry</i> , 76, pp.12-21.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Lugato E, Bampa F and Panagos P ; Montanarella L ; Jones A ;. (2014). Potential carbon sequestration of European arable soils estimated by modelling a comprehensive set of management practices. <i>Global Change Biology</i> , 20, pp.3557-3567.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Luo Z K, Wang E L; Baldock J and Xing H T;. (2014). Potential soil organic carbon stock and its uncertainty under various cropping systems in Australian cropland. <i>Soil Research</i> , 52, pp.463-475.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE

Luo S, Zhu L and Liu J ; Bu L ; Yue S ; Shen Y ; Li S ;. (2015). Sensitivity of soil organic carbon stocks and fractions to soil surface mulching in semiarid farmland. <i>European Journal of Soil ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Lupwayi N Z and Larney F J; Blackshaw R E; Pearson D C; Eastman A H;. (2018). Soil Microbial Biomass and Its Relationship with Yields of Irrigated Wheat under Long-term Conservation Management. <i>Soil Science</i> , 183(5), pp.179-187.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Microbial biomass carbon. SOC may be reported in Li L., F. J. Larney, D. A. Angers, D. C. Pearson, and R. E. Blackshaw. 2015. Surface soil quality attributes following 12 years of conventional and conservation management on irrigated rotations in southern Alberta. <i>Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.</i> 79:930–942.
Lutes K, Oelbermann M and Thevathasan N V; Gordon A M;. (2016). Effect of nitrogen fertilizer on greenhouse gas emissions in two willow clones (<i>Salix miyabeana</i> and <i>S-dasyclados</i>) in southern Ontario, Canada. <i>Agroforestry Systems</i> , 90, pp.785-796.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Lychuk T E, Moulin A P; Lemke R L; Gossen B D; Leeson J Y; Kirk A and Johnson E N; Olfert O O; Brandt S A; Thomas A G;. (2017). Effects of crop inputs, diversity, environment, and terrain on yield in an 18-yr study in the semi-arid Canadian Prairies. <i>Canadian Journal of Plant Science</i> , 97(4), pp.715-730.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No C or OM data reported
Lynch DH. (2014). Sustaining soil organic carbon, soil quality, and soil health in organic field crop management systems. : crcnetbase.com .	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Ma YC, Kong XW and Yang B ; Zhang XL ; Yan XY ; ;. (2013). Net global warming potential and greenhouse gas intensity of annual rice–wheat rotations with integrated soil–crop system management. : Elsevier.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Macdonald L M, Herrmann T and Baldock J A;. (2013). Combining management based indices with environmental parameters to explain regional variation in soil carbon under dryland cropping in South Australia. <i>Soil Research</i> , 51, pp.738-747.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Regional study
Macholdt J and Honermeier B . (2019). Stability analysis for grain yield of winter wheat in a long-term field experiment. <i>Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science</i> , 65(5), pp.686-699.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No C or OM data reported
Maestre FT, Escolar C and Guevara ML ; ;. (2013). Changes in biocrust cover drive carbon cycle responses to climate change in drylands. <i>Global change ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Mahmoodabadi M and Ahmadbeigi B . (2013). Dry and water-stable aggregates in different cultivation systems of arid region soils. <i>Arabian Journal of Geosciences</i> , 6, pp.2997-3002.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Bsk
Maiga A, Alhameid A and Singh S ; Polat A ; Singh J ; Kumar S ; Osborne S ;. (2019). Responses of soil organic carbon, aggregate stability, carbon and nitrogen fractions to 15 and 24 years of no-till diversified crop rotations. <i>Soil Research</i> , 57(2), pp.149-157.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Exclude on comparator (no continuous crop, Legume in all rotations, no perennial crop).
Maillard E, McConkey B G and Angers D A;. (2018). Each rotation phase can affect soil carbon balance differently over decades. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 98(3), pp.584-588.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Wheat-fallow rotations only, comparing different phases
Makovníková J, Kanianska R and Kizeková M ;. (2017). The ecosystem services supplied by soil in relation to land use. <i>Hungarian Geographical Bulletin</i> , 66(1), pp.37-42.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Maltais-Landry G, Scow K and Brennan E ;. (2014). Soil phosphorus mobilization in the rhizosphere of cover crops has little effect on phosphorus cycling in California agricultural soils. <i>Soil Biology and Biochemistry</i> , 78, pp.255-262.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Soil C measured but not reported. Cover crop study, no relevant comparator (?)
Mao R and Zeng D H. (2013). EFFECT OF LAND-USE CHANGE FROM CROPLAND TO POPLAR-BASED AGROFORESTRY ON SOIL PROPERTIES IN A SEMIARID REGION OF NORTHEAST CHINA. <i>Fresenius Environmental Bulletin</i> , 22, pp.1077-1084.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Mao DH, Wang ZM and Li L ; Miao ZH ; Ma WH ; ;. (2015). Soil organic carbon in the Sanjiang Plain of China: storage, distribution and controlling factors., , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Martínez J P, Barbieri P A; Sainz Rozas and H R ; Echeverría H E;. (2013). Inclusion of cover crops in cropping sequences with soybean predominance in the southeast of the humid argentine Pampa. <i>Open Agriculture Journal</i> , 7, pp.3-10.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Martinez I, Chervet A and Weisskopf P ; Sturny W G; Etana A ; Stettler M ; Forkman J ; Keller T ;. (2016). Two decades of no-till in the Oberacker long-term field experiment: Part I. Crop yield, soil organic carbon and nutrient distribution in the soil profile. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 163, pp.141-151.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation (6y), no comparator.
Martínez J M and Galantini J A; Duval M E;. (2017). Tillage effects on labile pools of soil organic nitrogen in a semi-humid climate of Argentina: A long-term field study. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Martínez-García L B, Korthals G and Brussaard L ; Jørgensen H B; De Deyn ; G B ;. (2018). Organic management and cover crop species steer soil microbial community structure and functionality along with soil organic matter properties. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 263, pp.7-17.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION 3-year cover crop study

Martin-Lammerding D, Tenorio J L and Albarran M M; Zambrana E ; Walter I ;. (2013). Influence of tillage practices on soil biologically active organic matter content over a growing season under semiarid Mediterranean climate. Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research, 11, pp.232-243.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Study period only one growing season.
Matheus R, Kantur D and Bora N ;. (2018). Innovation of the fallow system with the legume cover crop a season for improved physical properties of soil degraded on dryland farming. International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research, 7(7), pp.107-111.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Cover crop study, Climate Aw
Mayes M, Marin-Spiotta E and Szymanski L ; Erdogan M A; Ozdogan M ; Clayton M ;. (2014). Soil type mediates effects of land use on soil carbon and nitrogen in the Konya Basin, Turkey. Geoderma, 232, pp.517-527.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Mazzoncini M, Sapkota T B and Bärberi P ; Antichi D ; Risaliti R ;. (2011). Long-term effect of tillage, nitrogen fertilization and cover crops on soil organic carbon and total nitrogen content. Soil and Tillage Research, 114, pp.165-174.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Not a crop rotation study. Effects of tillage, N-fertilisation and cover crops evaluated.
Mazzoncini M, Antichi D and Di Bene ; C ; Risaliti R ; Petri M ; Bonari E ;. (2016). Soil carbon and nitrogen changes after 28 years of no-tillage management under Mediterranean conditions. European Journal of Agronomy, 77, pp.156-165.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation, no comparator.
Melero S, López-Bellido R J and López-Bellido L ; Muñoz-Romero V ; Moreno F ; Murillo J M;. (2011). Long-term effect of tillage, rotation and nitrogen fertiliser on soil quality in a Mediterranean Vertisol. Soil and Tillage Research, 114, pp.97-107.	-Exclude on OUTCOME SOC data not shown.
Merbach W, Herbst F and Eissner H ; Schmidt L ; Deubel A ;. (2013). Influence of different long-term mineral-organic fertilization on yield, nutrient balance and soil C and N contents of a sandy loess (Haplic Phaeozem) in middle Germany. Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science, 59, pp.1059-1072.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Miao S J, Qiao Y F; Li P and Han X Z; Tang C X;. (2017). Fallow associated with autumn-plough favors structure stability and storage of soil organic carbon compared to continuous maize cropping in Mollisols. Plant and Soil, 416(1-2), pp.27-38.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwb
Mirsky S B and Lanyon L E; Needelman B A;. (2008). Evaluating soil management using particulate and chemically labile soil organic matter fractions. Soil Science Society of America Journal, 72, pp.180-185.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No SOC or TOC only POM
Mirsky S B and Ryan M R; Teasdale J R; Curran W S; Reberg-Horton C S; Spargo J T; Wells M S; Keene C L; Moyer J W;. (2013). Overcoming Weed Management Challenges in Cover Crop-Based Organic Rotational No-Till Soybean Production in the Eastern United States. Weed Technology, 27, pp.193-203.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Mitchell J P, Shrestha A and Horwath W R; Southard R J; Madden N ; Veenstra J ; Munk D S;. (2015). Tillage and Cover Cropping Affect Crop Yields and Soil Carbon in the San Joaquin Valley, California. Agronomy Journal, 107, pp.588-596.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Effect of tillage and winter cover crop
Mitchell J P, Shrestha A and Mathesius K ; Scow K M;. (2017). Cover cropping and no-tillage improve soil health in an arid irrigated cropping system in California's San Joaquin Valley, USA. Soil and Tillage ..., , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk, cover crop study.
Mohanty S, Nayak AK and Kumar A ; Tripathi R ; ;. (2013). Carbon and nitrogen mineralization kinetics in soil of rice–rice system under long term application of chemical fertilizers and farmyard manure. European journal of soil ..., , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Monteleone M, Garofalo P and Rita A ; Cammerino B ; Libutti A ;. (2015). Cereal straw management: a trade-off between energy and agronomic fate. Italian Journal of Agronomy, 10, pp.59-66.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION LCA
Moore E B and Wiedenhoef M H; Kaspar T C; Cambardella C A;. (2014). Rye Cover Crop Effects on Soil Quality in No-Till Corn Silage-Soybean Cropping Systems. Soil Science Society of America Journal, 78, pp.968-976.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR According to the original protocol the effect of cover crops is not relevant here. Moreover the study length is below 10 years.
Moore A D. (2014). The case for and against perennial forages in the Australian sheep-wheat zone: modelling livestock production, business risk and environmental interactions. Animal Production Science, 54, pp.2029-2041.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Motschenbacher J M and Brye K R; Anders M M; Gbur E E; Slaton N A; Evans-White M A;. (2013). Rice Rotation and Tillage Effects on Water-Stable Soil Macroaggregates and Their Associated Carbon and Nitrogen Contents in a Silt-Loam Soil. Soil Science, 178, pp.596-611.	-Exclude on SOIL TYPE Paddy soil ("in rice, a 5- to 10-cm-deep permanent flood was established and maintained until the rice reached physiological maturity.")
Mtyobile M, Muzangwa L and Mnkeni P N. S;. (2019). Tillage and Crop Rotation Effects on Selected Soil Chemical Properties and Wheat Yield in a Sandy Loam Oakleaf Soil in the Eastern Cape, South Africa. International Journal of Agriculture and Biology, 21(2), pp.367-374.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Only 3 years
Muhlbachova G, Kusa H and Ruzek P ;. (2015). Soil characteristics and crop yields under different tillage techniques. Plant Soil and Environment, 61, pp.566-572.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study

Mukherjee A and Lal R. (2015). Tillage effects on quality of organic and mineral soils under on-farm conditions in Ohio. <i>Environmental Earth Sciences</i> , 74, pp.1815-1822.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study
Mulvaney M J, Wood C W; Balkcom K S; Kemble J and Shannon D A;. (2017). No-till with high biomass cover crops and invasive legume mulches increased total soil carbon after three years of collard production. <i>Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems</i> , 41, pp.30-45.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Muminov M A, Guo L and Song Y ; Gu X ; Cen Y ; Meng J ; Jiang G ;. (2018). Comparisons of weed community, soil health and economic performance between wheat-maize and garlic-soybean rotation systems under different weed managements. <i>PeerJ</i> , 2018(5), pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Munkholm L J and Heck R J; Deen B. (2013). Long-term rotation and tillage effects on soil structure and crop yield. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 127, pp.85-91.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Soil C not reported in any form.
Muñoz-Rojas M, Jordán A and Zavala LM ; ;. (2015). Impact of land use and land cover changes on organic carbon stocks in Mediterranean soils (1956–2007). <i>Land Degradation & ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Regional soil survey
Munoz-Romero V, Lopez-Bellido R J and Fernandez-Garcia P ; Redondo R ; Murillo S ; Lopez-Bellido L ;. (2017). Effects of tillage, crop rotation and N application rate on labile and recalcitrant soil carbon in a Mediterranean Vertisol. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 169, pp.118-123.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No SOC data reported for individual rotations.
Murthy IK, Gupta M and Tomar S ; Munsu M ; ;. (2013). Carbon sequestration potential of agroforestry systems in India. : <i>researchgate.net</i> .	-Exclude on REVIEW
Muzangwa L, Mkeni P N. S and Chiduzo C ;. (2019). The Use of Residue Retention and Inclusion of Legumes to Improve Soil Biological Activity in Maize-Based No-Till Systems of the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. <i>Agricultural Research</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Only 2 years!
Naab J B, Mahama G Y; Yahaya I and Prasad P V. V;. (2017). Conservation Agriculture Improves Soil Quality, Crop Yield, and Incomes of Smallholder Farmers in North Western Ghana. <i>Frontiers in Plant Science</i> , 8, pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Nachimuthu G, Hulugalle N R and Watkins M D; Finlay L A; McCorkell B ;. (2018). Irrigation induced surface carbon flow in a Vertisol under furrow irrigated cotton cropping systems. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 183, pp.8-18.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No SOC data reported.
Nadimi-Goki M, Bini C and Wahsha M ; Kato Y ; Fornasier F ;. (2018). Enzyme dynamics in contaminated paddy soils under different cropping patterns (NE Italy). <i>Journal of Soils and Sediments</i> , 18(6), pp.2157-2171.	-Exclude on SOIL TYPE
Nagler M, Fontana V and Lair G J; Radtke A ; Tasser E ; Zerbe S ; Tappeiner U ;. (2015). Different management of larch grasslands in the European Alps shows low impact on above- and belowground carbon stocks. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 213, pp.186-193.	-Exclude on CLIMATE ET
Nandan R, Singh V and Singh S S; Kumar V ; Hazra K K; Nath C P; Poonia S ; Malik R K; Bhattacharyya R ; McDonald A ;. (2019). Impact of conservation tillage in rice-based cropping systems on soil aggregation, carbon pools and nutrients. <i>Geoderma</i> , 340, pp.104-114.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Nash P R and Gollany H T; Sainju U M;. (2018). CQESTR-Simulated Response of Soil Organic Carbon to Management, Yield, and Climate Change in the Northern Great Plains Region. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 47(4), pp.674-683.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 6-year study
Nash P R and Gollany H T; Novak J M; Bauer P J; Hunt P G; Karlen D L;. (2018). Simulated Soil Organic Carbon Response to Tillage, Yield, and Climate Change in the Southeastern Coastal Plains. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 47(4), pp.663-673.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one (but changing) rotation during 2002-2013
Nath C P, Hazra K K; Kumar N and Praharaj C S; Singh S S; Singh U ; Singh N P;. (2019). Including grain legume in rice-wheat cropping system improves soil organic carbon pools over time. <i>Ecological Engineering</i> , 129, pp.144-153.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Navarro-Noya YE, Gómez-Acata S and ;. (2013). Relative impacts of tillage, residue management and crop-rotation on soil bacterial communities in a semi-arid agroecosystem. <i>Soil Biology and ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwb
Nawaz A, Farooq M and Lal R ; Rehman A ; Hafeez ur ; Rehman ;. (2017). Comparison of conventional and conservation rice-wheat systems in Punjab, Pakistan. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 169, pp.35-43.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Negm L M and Youssef M A; Skaggs R W; Chescheir G M; Jones J. (2014). DRAINMOD-DSSAT model for simulating hydrology, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, and crop growth for drained crop land. <i>Agricultural Water Management</i> , 137, pp.30-45.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR corn-soybean, no comparator
Nelson R G, Tatarko J and Ascough J C;. (2015). SOIL EROSION AND ORGANIC MATTER VARIATIONS FOR CENTRAL GREAT PLAINS CROPPING SYSTEMS UNDER RESIDUE REMOVAL. <i>Transactions of the Asabe</i> , 58, pp.415-427.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Neugschwandtner R W, Liebhard P and Kaul H P; Wagentristl H ;. (2014). Soil chemical properties as affected by tillage and crop in a long-term field experiment. <i>Plant Soil and Environment</i> , 60, pp.57-62.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 7-year study

Nieto OM, Castro J and Fernández-Ondoño E ;. (2013). Conventional tillage versus cover crops in relation to carbon fixation in Mediterranean olive cultivation. Plant and soil, , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Njaimwe A N, Mnkeni P N. S; Chiduzo C and Muchaonyerwa P ; Wakindiki I I. C;. (2016). Tillage and crop rotation effects on carbon sequestration and aggregate stability in two contrasting soils at the Zanyokwe Irrigation Scheme, Eastern Cape province, South Africa. South African Journal of Plant and Soil, 33, pp.317-324.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Njaimwe A N, Mnkeni P N. S; Muchaonyerwa P and Chiduzo C ; Wakindiki I I. C;. (2018). Sensitivity of selected chemical and biological soil quality parameters to tillage and rotational cover cropping at the Zanyokwe Irrigation Scheme, South Africa. South African Journal of Plant and Soil, 35(5), pp.321-328.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Only 3 years
Norman C R and Brye K R; Gbur E E; Chen P Y; Rupe J. (2016). Long-term Management Effects on Soil Properties and Yields in a Wheat-Soybean Double-Crop System in Eastern Arkansas. Soil Science, 181, pp.1-12.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Not a crop rotation study.
Notaro K A, de Medeiros and E V ; Duda G P; Moreira K A; de Barros ; J A ; dos Santos ; U J ; Lima J R. D; Moraes W D;. (2018). Enzymatic activity, microbial biomass, and organic carbon of Entisols from Brazilian tropical dry forest and annual and perennial crops. Chilean Journal of Agricultural Research, 78(1), pp.68-77.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Land use study, climate As
Nouri A, Lee J and Yin X H; Saxton A M; Tyler D D; Sykes V R; Arelli P ;. (2019). Crop species in no-tillage summer crop rotations affect soil quality and yield in an Alfisol. Geoderma, 345, pp.51-62.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No carbon measures what so ever!
Novelli L E and Caviglia O P; Wilson M G; Sasal M C;. (2013). Land use intensity and cropping sequence effects on aggregate stability and C storage in a Vertisol and a Mollisol. Geoderma, 195, pp.260-267.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Novelli L E and Caviglia O P; Pineiro G. (2017). Increased cropping intensity improves crop residue inputs to the soil and aggregate-associated soil organic carbon stocks. Soil & Tillage Research, 165, pp.128-136.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study
Nyawade S O, Gachene C K. K; Karanja N N; Gitari H I; Schulte-Geldermann E and Parker M L;. (2019). Controlling soil erosion in smallholder potato farming systems using legume intercrops. Geoderma Regional, 17, pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Only 1 year
Obade V D and Lal R. (2014). Soil quality evaluation under different land management practices. Environmental Earth Sciences, 72, pp.4531-4549.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Comparator and intervention in different locations and soil types, not replicated at each site. Duration of intervention not reported but probably variable.
Oberholzer H R, Leifeld J and Mayer J ;. (2014). Changes in soil carbon and crop yield over 60 years in the Zurich Organic Fertilization Experiment, following land-use change from grassland to cropland. Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science, 177, pp.696-704.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation (8y). The only comparator available is grassland (before).
Oelbermann M, Regehr A and Echarte L ;. (2015). Changes in soil characteristics after six seasons of cereal-legume intercropping in the Southern Pampa. Geoderma Regional, 4, pp.100-107.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 6-year study
Oelbermann M, Echarte L and Marroquin L ; Morgan S ; Regehr A ; Vachon K E; Wilton M ;. (2017). Estimating soil carbon dynamics in intercrop and sole crop agroecosystems using the Century model. Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science, , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Ohland Tatiane, do Carmo Lana and Maria ; Fernando Frandoloso ; Jucenei ;. (2019). Fracionamento quimico da matéria orgânica do solo após sistemas de manejo no inverno. Chemical Fractions of Soil Organic Matter after Management Systems in Winter., 18(1), pp.53-64.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR All rotations include soybean
Ojeda J J and Caviglia O P; Agnusdei M G;. (2018). Vertical distribution of root biomass and soil carbon stocks in forage cropping systems. Plant and Soil, 423(1-2), pp.175-191.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study (2012-2014)
Okebalama C B and Igwe C A; Okolo C C;. (2017). Soil organic carbon levels in soils of contrasting land uses in southeastern Nigeria. : redalyc.org.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Land-use soil survey
Olson KR, Ebelhar SA and Lang JM ;. (2013). Effects of 24 years of conservation tillage systems on soil organic carbon and soil productivity. Applied and Environmental Soil ..., , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Tillage study on Corn-soybean rotations
Olson K R and Al-Kaisi M M;. (2015). The importance of soil sampling depth for accurate account of soil organic carbon sequestration, storage, retention and loss. Catena, 125, pp.33-37.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR maize and soybean in tillage study
Ortiz C, Vazquez E and Rubio A ; Benito M ; Schindlbacher A ; Jandl R ; Butterbach-Bahl K ; Diaz-Pines E ;. (2016). Soil organic matter dynamics after afforestation of mountain grasslands in both a Mediterranean and temperate climate. Biogeochemistry, 131, pp.267-280.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Ouyang W, Xu Y and Hao F ; Wang X ; Siyang C ; Lin C ;. (2013). Effect of long-term agricultural cultivation and land use conversion on soil nutrient contents in the Sanjiang Plain. Catena, , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Ozgoz E, Gunal H and Acir N ; Gokmen F ; Birol M ; Budak M ;. (2013). SOIL QUALITY AND SPATIAL VARIABILITY ASSESSMENT OF LAND USE EFFECTS IN A TYPIC HAPLUSTOLL. Land Degradation & Development, 24, pp.277-286.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Farmland vs pasture. No detailed info on rotations.

Pacaldo RS, Volk TA and Briggs RD ;. (2013). No significant differences in soil organic carbon contents along a chronosequence of shrub willow biomass crop fields. <i>Biomass and Bioenergy</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Continous shrub willow monoculture, no crop rotation.
Pacaldo RS, Volk TA and Briggs RD ;. (2014). Carbon sequestration in fine roots and foliage biomass offsets soil CO2 effluxes along a 19-year chronosequence of shrub willow (<i>Salix x dasyclados</i>) biomass crops. <i>BioEnergy Research</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Only continous monoculture (shrub willow), no crop rotation.
Paetsch L, Mueller C W and Rumpel C ; Houot S ; Kogel-Knabner I ;. (2016). Urban waste composts enhance OC and N stocks after long-term amendment but do not alter organic matter composition. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 223, pp.211-222.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Palosuo T, Heikkinen J and Regina K ;. (2015). Method for estimating soil carbon stock changes in Finnish mineral cropland and grassland soils. <i>Carbon Management</i> , 6, pp.207-220.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Modelling study, no info on rotations.
Pan F J, Li N and Zou W X ; Han X Z ; McLaughlin N B ;. (2016). Soil nematode community structure and metabolic footprint in the early pedogenesis of a Mollisol. <i>European Journal of Soil Biology</i> , 77, pp.17-25.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwb
Pardo G, del Prado and A ; Martinez-Mena M ; Bustamante M A ; Martin J A R ; Alvaro-Fuentes J ; Moral R ;. (2017). Orchard and horticulture systems in Spanish Mediterranean coastal areas: Is there a real possibility to contribute to C sequestration?. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 238, pp.153-167.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Parihar C M, Yadav M R ; Jat S L ; Singh A K ; Kumar B and Pradhan S ; Chakraborty D ; Jat M L ; Jat R K ; Saharawat Y S ; Yadav O P ;. (2016). Long term effect of conservation agriculture in maize rotations on total organic carbon, physical and biological properties of a sandy loam soil in north-western Indo-Gangetic Plains. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 161, pp.116-128.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Parihar C M, Yadav M R ; Jat S L ; Singh A K ; Kumar B and Pooniya V ; Pradhan S ; Verma R K ; Jat M L ; Jat R K ; Parihar M D ; Nayak H S ; Saharawat Y S ;. (2018). Long-Term Conservation Agriculture and Intensified Cropping Systems: Effects on Growth, Yield, Water, and Energy-use Efficiency of Maize in Northwestern India. <i>Pedosphere</i> , 28(6), pp.952-963.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Parihar C M and Parihar M D ; Sapkota T B ; Nanwal R K ; Singh A K ; Jat S L ; Nayak H S ; Mahala D M ; Singh L K ; Kakraliya S K ; Stirling C M ; Jat M L ;. (2018). Long-term impact of conservation agriculture and diversified maize rotations on carbon pools and stocks, mineral nitrogen fractions and nitrous oxide fluxes in inceptisol of India. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 640, pp.1382-1392.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study (2008-2013)
Pariz C M, Costa C and Crusciol C A. C ; Meirelles P R. L ; Castilhos A M ; Andreotti M ; Costa N R ; Martello J M ; Souza D M ; Protes V M ; Longhini V Z ; Franzluebbbers A J ;. (2017). Production, nutrient cycling and soil compaction to grazing of grass companion cropping with corn and soybean. <i>Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems</i> , 108(1), pp.35-54.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study (2010-2013)
Parras-Alcántara L, Lozano-García B and Brevik EC ; ;. (2015). Soil organic carbon stocks assessment in Mediterranean natural areas: a comparison of entire soil profiles and soil control sections. <i>Journal of ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Natural soils
Partey S T, Zougmore R B ; Ouedraogo M and Thevathasan N V ;. (2017). Why Promote Improved Fallows as a Climate-Smart Agroforestry Technology in Sub-Saharan Africa?. <i>Sustainability</i> , 9(11), pp..	-Exclude on REVIEW
Pezzuolo A, Dumont B and Sartori L ; Marinello F ;. (2017). Evaluating the impact of soil conservation measures on soil organic carbon at the farm scale. ... and <i>Electronics in ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 4-year study (2010-2014)
Phillips R L and Eken M R ; West M S ;. (2015). Soil Organic Carbon Beneath Croplands and Re-established Grasslands in the North Dakota Prairie Pothole Region. <i>Environmental Management</i> , 55, pp.1191-1199.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Cropland vs. CRP (re-established grassland). No detailed info on rotations.
Pihlap E, Vuko M and Lucas M ; Steffens M ; Schloter M ; Vetterlein D ; Endenich M ; Kögel-Knabner I ;. (2019). Initial soil formation in an agriculturally reclaimed open-cast mining area - the role of management and loess parent material. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 191, pp.224-237.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Plaza C, Courtier-Murias D and Fernandez J M ; Polo A ; Simpson A J ;. (2013). Physical, chemical, and biochemical mechanisms of soil organic matter stabilization under conservation tillage systems: A central role for microbes and microbial by-products in C sequestration. <i>Soil Biology & Biochemistry</i> , 57, pp.124-134.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Tillage study. All plots were under continuous winter barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> L.).
Plaza-Bonilla D, Cantero-Martínez C and Viñas P ; ;. (2013). Soil aggregation and organic carbon protection in a no-tillage chronosequence under Mediterranean conditions. <i>Geoderma</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study (no till chronosequence experiment). In all five chronosequence phases the cropping system consisted in winter cereal rotation.
Plaza-Bonilla D, Nolot J M and Passot S ; Raffaillac D ; Justes E ;. (2016). Grain legume-based rotations managed under conventional tillage need cover crops to mitigate soil organic matter losses. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 156, pp.33-43.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE

Plénet D, Lubet E and Juste C ;. (1993). Change in the organic carbon content of soil in a long-term continuous non-irrigated maize crop. Evolution à long terme du statut carboné du sol en monoculture non irriguée du maïs (Zea mays L), 13, pp.685-698.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION The rotations we can use are not different (monocultures of maize with or without residues return).
Poeplau Christopher and Don Axel . (2013). Soil carbon changes under Miscanthus driven by C4 accumulation and C3 decomposition – toward a default sequestration function. GCB Bioenergy, , pp.n/a-n/a.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Unreplicated studies at six different sites. Only differences reported for each site. No measure of variability at each site.
Poeplau C and Don A . (2014). Soil carbon changes under Miscanthus driven by C-4 accumulation and C-3 decomposition - toward a default sequestration function. Global Change Biology Bioenergy, 6, pp.327-338.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Poeplau C and Don A . (2015). Carbon sequestration in agricultural soils via cultivation of cover crops - A meta-analysis. Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment, 200, pp.33-41.	-Exclude on REVIEW Meta-analysis of cover crop studies
Pooniya V, Choudhary A K and Swarnalakshmi K ;. (2017). High-Value Crops Imbedded Intensive Cropping Systems for Enhanced Productivity, Resource-Use-Efficiency, Energetics and Soil-Health in Indo-Gangetic Plains. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences India Section B - Biological Sciences, 87(4), pp.1073-1090.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Prade T, Katterer T and Bjornsson L ;. (2017). Including a one-year grass ley increases soil organic carbon and decreases greenhouse gas emissions from cereal-dominated rotations - A Swedish farm case study. Biosystems Engineering, 164, pp.200-212.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No measured SOC data
Prado B, Fuentes M and Verhulst N ; Govaerts B ; De Leon ; F ; Zamora O ;. (2014). Fate of atrazine in a soil under different agronomic management practices. Journal of Environmental Science and Health Part B-Pesticides Food Contaminants and Agricultural Wastes, 49, pp.844-855.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Prajapat K, Vyas A K and Dhar S ; Jain N K ; Hashim M ; Choudhary G L ;. (2018). Energy input-output relationship of soybean-based cropping systems under different nutrient supply options. Journal of Environmental Biology, 39(1), pp.93-101.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study (2011-2013)
Priyanka K and Anshumali . (2018). Quantifying total and labile pools of soil organic carbon in cultivated and uncultivated soils in eastern India. Soil Research, 56(4), pp.413-420.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa/Aw
Pugesgaard S, Petersen S O and Chirinda N ;. (2017). Crop residues as driver for N2O emissions from a sandy loam soil. Agricultural and forest ..., , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR alle 4 rotations include leguminous plants
Qiao Y F, Miao S J ; Li N and Xu Y L ; Han X Z ; Zhang B ;. (2015). Crop species affect soil organic carbon turnover in soil profile and among aggregate sizes in a Mollisol as estimated from natural C-13 abundance. Plant and Soil, 392, pp.163-174.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwb
Qiao Y F and Miao S J ; Li Y X ; Zhong X. (2018). Chemical composition of soil organic carbon changed by long-term monoculture cropping system in Chinese black soil. Plant Soil and Environment, 64(11), pp.557-563.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Qin H, Lu K P and Strong P J ; Xu Q F ; Wu Q F ; Xu Z X ; Xu J ; Wang H L ;. (2015). Long-term fertilizer application effects on the soil, root arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and community composition in rotation agriculture. Applied Soil Ecology, 89, pp.35-43.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Fertilizer study on winter wheat - rice rotations
Qin Z C, Dunn J B ; Kwon H Y ; Mueller S and Wander M M ;. (2016). Soil carbon sequestration and land use change associated with biofuel production: empirical evidence. Global Change Biology Bioenergy, 8, pp.66-80.	-Exclude on REVIEW Individual crops, not rotations
Qin S J and Jiao K B ; He J L ; Lyu D G ;. (2016). Forage crops alter soil bacterial and fungal communities in an apple orchard. Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica Section B-Soil and Plant Science, 66, pp.229-236.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Intercropping of cover crops and apple trees
Raave H, Keres I and Kauer K ; Nöges M ; ;. (2014). The impact of activated carbon on NO3--N, NH4+-N, P and K leaching in relation to fertilizer use. ... journal of soil ..., , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Rabbi SMF, Tighe M and Cowie A ; Wilson BR ; ;. (2014). The relationships between land uses, soil management practices, and soil carbon fractions in South Eastern Australia. Agriculture and Ecosystems ..., , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Soil survey
Ran Y, Deutsch L and Lannerstad M ; Heinke J ;. (2013). Rapidly intensified beef production in Uruguay: Impacts on water-related ecosystem services. In: Lundqvist J, ed., At the Confluence - Selection from the 2012 World Water Week. Amsterdam: Elsevier Science Bv, pp.77-87.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Data taken from other studies.
Raphael J P. A, Calonego J C ; Milori Dmbp and Rosolem C A ;. (2016). Soil organic matter in crop rotations under no-till. Soil & Tillage Research, 155, pp.45-53.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-yr cycle
Ren Z, Gao B and Huang T ; Ju X ;. (2014). The contribution of root respiration to soil respiration under different crop rotations and managements. Huanjing Kexue Xuebao/Acta Scientiae Circumstantiae, 34, pp.2367-2375.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Chinese
Reville A, Emmel C and D'Odorico P ; Buchmann N ; Hortnagl L ; Eugster W ;. (2019). Estimating cropland carbon fluxes: A process-based model	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation

evaluation at a Swiss crop-rotation site. <i>Field Crops Research</i> , 234, pp.95-106.	
Reynolds B, Chamberlain PM and Poskitt J ; ;. (2013). Countryside survey: national "soil change" 1978–2007 for topsoils in great britain—acidity, carbon, and total nitrogen status. <i>Vadose Zone ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Regional study
Richards M, Pogson M and Dondini M ; Jones E O; Hastings A ; Henner D N; Tallis M J; Casella E ; Matthews R W; Henshall P A; Milner S ; Taylor G ; McNamara N P; Smith J U; Smith P ;. (2017). High-resolution spatial modelling of greenhouse gas emissions from land-use change to energy crops in the United Kingdom. <i>GCB Bioenergy</i> , 9, pp.627-644.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Rigon J P. G, Calonego J C; Rosolem C A; La Scala and N ;. (2018). Cover crop rotations in no-till system: short-term CO2 emissions and soybean yield. <i>Scientia Agricola</i> , 75(1), pp.18-26.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No Soil C or OM data reported, also climate Aw
Ritchey E L and Tyler D D; Essington M E; Mullen M D; Saxton A M;. (2015). Nitrogen Rate, Cover Crop, and Tillage Practice Alter Soil Chemical Properties. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 107, pp.1259-1268.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE Annual cotton production with different cover crops
Robertson F, Armstrong R and Partington D ; Perris R ; Oliver I ; Aumann C ; Crawford D ; Rees D ;. (2015). Effect of cropping practices on soil organic carbon: evidence from long-term field experiments in Victoria, Australia. <i>Soil Research</i> , 53, pp.636-646.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Robertson F, Crawford D and Partington D ; Oliver I ; Rees D ; Aumann C ; Armstrong R ; Perris R ; Davey M ; Moodie M ; Baldock J ;. (2016). Soil organic carbon in cropping and pasture systems of Victoria, Australia. <i>Soil Research</i> , 54, pp.64-77.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Continuous cropping vs cropping-pasture rotations, soil survey study. No control on the history of the sampled sites. No replication. This is not a replicated field study and is outside the inclusion criteria specified in the protocol: "Field studies examining interventions that have lasted at least 10 years to ensure that changes in soil carbon are detectable".
Robertson A D, Zhang Y and Sherrod L A; Rosenzweig S T; Ma L W; Ahuja L ; Schipanski M E;. (2018). Climate Change Impacts on Yields and Soil Carbon in Row Crop Dryland Agriculture. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 47(4), pp.684-694.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Romanenkova V, Belichenko M and Petrova A ; Raskatova T ; Jahn G ; Krasilnikov P ;. (2019). Soil organic carbon dynamics in long-term experiments with mineral and organic fertilizers in Russia. <i>Geoderma Regional</i> , 17, pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation at each site
Romero C M, Engel R E; D'Andrilli J and Chen C C; Zabinski C ; Miller P R; Wallander R ;. (2017). Bulk optical characterization of dissolved organic matter from semiarid wheat-based cropping systems. <i>Geoderma</i> , 306, pp.40-49.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Only DOC is given for each of the rotations
Rosenzweig S T and Fonte S J; Schipanski M E;. (2018). Intensifying rotations increases soil carbon, fungi, and aggregation in semi-arid agroecosystems. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 258, pp.14-22.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Regional study
Rosset J S, Guareschi R F; Pinto Ladr and Pereira M G; Lana M D;. (2016). Phosphorus fractions and correlation with soil attributes in a chronosequence of agricultural under no-tillage. <i>Semina-Ciencias Agrarias</i> , 37, pp.3915-3926.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Tillage study with corn/wheat-soya
Rotich H K, Onwonga R and Mbau J S; Koeh O K;. (2018). Soil organic carbon content and stocks in relation to grazing management in semi-arid grasslands of Kenya. <i>Journal of Rangeland Science</i> , 8(2), pp.143-155.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh/Aw
Rowe R L, Keith A M; Elias D and Dondini M ; Smith P ; Oxley J ; McNamara N P;. (2016). Initial soil C and land-use history determine soil C sequestration under perennial bioenergy crops. <i>Global Change Biology Bioenergy</i> , 8, pp.1046-1060.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR SRC compared to arable land, unclear what rotation arable land represents.
Ruehlmann J. (2013). The Box Plot Experiment in Grossbeeren after eight rotations: nitrogen, carbon and energy balances. <i>Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science</i> , 59, pp.1159-1176.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Ryals R, Kaiser M and Torn MS ; Berhe AA ; ;. (2014). Impacts of organic matter amendments on carbon and nitrogen dynamics in grassland soils. <i>Soil Biology and ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Ryschawy J, Liebbig M A and Kronberg S L; Archer D W; Hendrickson J R;. (2017). Integrated Crop-Livestock Management Effects on Soil Quality Dynamics in a Semiarid Region: A Typology of Soil Change over Time. <i>Applied and Environmental Soil Science</i> , 2017, pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR the "comparator" is a permanent grassland
Safadoust A, Doaei N and Mahboubi A A; Mosaddeghi M R; Gharabaghi B ; Voroney P ; Ahrens B ;. (2016). Long-term cultivation and landscape position effects on aggregate size and organic carbon fractionation on surface soil properties in semi-arid region of Iran. <i>Arid Land Research and Management</i> , 30, pp.345-361.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Wheat cropping vs pasture
Sainju U M and Senwo Z N; Nyakatawa E Z; Tazisong I A; Reddy K C;. (2008). Tillage, cropping systems, and nitrogen fertilizer source effects on soil carbon sequestration and fractions. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 37, pp.880-888.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only contrasts between groups of treatments vs fallow reported.

Sainju U M, Allen B A; Caesar-TonThat T and Lenssen A W;. (2015). Dryland Soil Carbon and Nitrogen after Thirty Years of Tillage and Cropping Sequence Combination. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 107, pp.1822-1830.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR No continuous cropping. Only rotations not including any legumes or perennials.
Salazar O, Balboa L and Peralta K ; Rossi M ; Casanova M ; Tapia Y ; Singh R ; Quemada M ;. (2019). Effect of cover crops on leaching of dissolved organic nitrogen and carbon in a maize-cover crop rotation in Mediterranean Central Chile. <i>Agricultural Water Management</i> , 212, pp.399-406.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE The study was conducted in a temperature-controlled glasshouse(25 °C), on undisturbed soil columns packed in PVC tubes (0.2m diameter, 0.5m long), at the Antumapu Experimental Station located in Santiago, Chile (33°34'S, 70°38'W).
Salembier C, Elverdin J H and Meynard J M;. (2016). Tracking on-farm innovations to unearth alternatives to the dominant soybean-based system in the Argentinean Pampa. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i> , 36, pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Salvo L, Terra J A and Ayala W ; Bermudez R ; Correa J ;. (2008). Long-term phosphorus fertilization and perennial legumes addition impacts on a temperate natural grassland: II . Total and particulate soil organic carbon. In: <i>Proceedings of the XXI</i> , pp.. function URL() { [native code] }.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Sanchez-Gonzalez A, Chapela-Lara M and German-Venegas E ; Fuentes-Garcia R ; del Rio-Portilla ; F ; Siebe C ;. (2017). Changes in quality and quantity of soil organic matter stocks resulting from wastewater irrigation in formerly forested land. <i>Geoderma</i> , 306, pp.99-107.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Sanchez-Navarro V, Zornoza R and Faz A ; Fernandez J A;. (2019). Comparing legumes for use in multiple cropping to enhance soil organic carbon, soil fertility, aggregates stability and vegetables yields under semi-arid conditions. <i>Scientia Horticulturae</i> , 246, pp.835-841.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSk
Sanderman J and Chappell A . (2013). Uncertainty in soil carbon accounting due to unrecognized soil erosion. <i>Global change biology</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Continous wheat
Santin-Montanya M I, Martin-Lammerding D and Zambrana E ; Tenorio J L;. (2016). Management of weed emergence and weed seed bank in response to different tillage, cropping systems and selected soil properties. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 161, pp.38-46.	-Exclude on OUTCOME Soil carbon is given in C-POM.
Sapkota T B, Mazzoncini M and Barberi P ; Antichi D ; Silvestri N ;. (2012). Fifteen years of no till increase soil organic matter, microbial biomass and arthropod diversity in cover crop-based arable cropping systems. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i> , 32, pp.853-863.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Identical rotations (m-dw-sf-dw) with different cover crops. No eligible comparator.
Sarapatka B and Cizkova S . (2014). The influence of different types of grassland on soil quality in upland areas of Czech Republic. <i>Journal of Environmental Biology</i> , 35, pp.453-459.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Grassland soil survey
Sarkar D, Meitei C B and Das A ; Ghosh P K; Mandal B ;. (2018). Changes in soil organic carbon pools in a long-term trial with perennial fodder crops in acid soils of north-east India. <i>Grass and Forage Science</i> , 73(2), pp.473-481.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Sarker J R, Singh B P; Dougherty W J; Fang Y Y; Badgery W and Hoyled F C; Dalal R C; Cowie A L;. (2018). Impact of agricultural management practices on the nutrient supply potential of soil organic matter under long-term farming systems. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 175, pp.71-81.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Only one of the sites are within our climate, and that site only use one rotation
Sarker J R, Singh B P; Cowie A L; Fang Y Y; Collins D and Badgery W ; Dalal R C;. (2018). Agricultural management practices impacted carbon and nutrient concentrations in soil aggregates, with minimal influence on aggregate stability and total carbon and nutrient stocks in contrasting soils. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 178, pp.209-223.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Only monoculture at the field site that is within "our" climate
Sarker J R, Singh B P; Fang Y Y; Cowie A L; Dougherty W J; Collins D and Dalal R C; Singh B K;. (2019). Tillage history and crop residue input enhanced native carbon mineralisation and nutrient supply in contrasting soils under long-term farming systems. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 193, pp.71-84.	-Exclude on OUTCOME C mineralisation rates, not possible to compare different crop rotations
Sato JH, Figueiredo CC and Marchão RL ; Madari BE ;;. (2014). Methods of soil organic carbon determination in Brazilian savannah soils. : <i>SciELO Brasil</i> .	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Sato J H, de Figueiredo and C C ; Marchão R L; de Oliveira ; A D ; Vilela L ; Delvico F M; Alves B J. R; de Carvalho ; A M ;;. (2019). Understanding the relations between soil organic matter fractions and N2O emissions in a long-term integrated crop–livestock system. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Aw
Scalise A, Tortorella D and Pristeri A ; Petrovicova B ; Gelsomino A ; Lindstrom K ; Monti M ;. (2015). Legume-barley intercropping stimulates soil N supply and crop yield in the succeeding durum wheat in a rotation under rainfed conditions. <i>Soil Biology & Biochemistry</i> , 89, pp.150-161.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Intercropping, intervention <10 years.
Schierhorn F, Müller D and Beringer T ;;. (2013). Post-Soviet cropland abandonment and carbon sequestration in European Russia, Ukraine, and Belarus. : <i>Wiley Online Library</i> .	-Exclude on INTERVENTION carbon sequestration related to cropland abandonment. No detailed info on rotations.
Schimel JP and Schaeffer SM . (2015). Microbial control over carbon cycling in soil. The causes and consequences of ..., , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION

Schmer M R and Vogel K P; Varvel G E; Follett R F; Mitchell R B; Jin V L;. (2014). Energy Potential and Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Bioenergy Cropping Systems on Marginally Productive Cropland. <i>Plos One</i> , 9, pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Fertilizer and harvest treatment study on corn and switchgrass
Schwartz R C, Baumhardt R L; Scanlon B R; Bell J M; Davis R G; Ibragimov N and Jones O R; Reedy R C;. (2015). Long-Term Changes in Soil Organic Carbon and Nitrogen under Semiarid Tillage and Cropping Practices. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 79, pp.1771-1781.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Climate zone BSk. Also not possible to compare rotations.
Sebilo M, Mayer B and Nicolardot B ; ;. (2013). Long-term fate of nitrate fertilizer in agricultural soils. <i>Proceedings of the ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Semenov V M and Kogut B M; Zinyakova N B; Masyutenko N P; Malyukova L S; Lebedeva T N; Tulina A S;. (2018). Biologically Active Organic Matter in Soils of European Russia. <i>Eurasian Soil Science</i> , 51(4), pp.434-447.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Soil survey, not possible to compare crop rotations
Senapati N, Chabbi A and Smith P ;. (2018). Modelling daily to seasonal carbon fluxes and annual net ecosystem carbon balance of cereal grain-cropland using DailyDayCent: A model data comparison. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 252, pp.159-177.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Seremešić S, Milošev D and Ćirić V ; Đalović I ;. (2015). SIMULATION OF YIELD AND CONTENT OF SOIL ORGANIC CARBON FROM A LONG-TERM EXPERIMENT "CROP ROTATION" USING DNDC MODEL. VII SIMPOZIJUM sa ... , pp..	-Exclude on LANGUAGE
Setia R, Gottschalk P and Smith P ; Marschner P ; ;. (2013). Soil salinity decreases global soil organic carbon stocks. <i>Science of The Total ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Shangguan W, Dai Y and Liu B ; Zhu A ; ;. (2013). A China data set of soil properties for land surface modeling. : Wiley Online Library.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Sharifi M, Lynch D H and Hammermeister A ; Burton D L; Messiga A J;. (2014). Effect of green manure and supplemental fertility amendments on selected soil quality parameters in an organic potato rotation in Eastern Canada. <i>Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems</i> , 100, pp.135-146.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 5-year study
Sharkov I N and Samokhvalova L M; Mishina P V; Shepelev A G;. (2014). Effect of crop residues on the organic matter composition of a leached chernozem in the Western Siberian forest-steppe. <i>Eurasian Soil Science</i> , 47, pp.304-309.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE <10 yr. Also, number of true replicates unclear.
Sharma S D, Kumar P and Bhardwaj S K; Chandel A ;. (2015). Agronomic performance, nutrient cycling and microbial biomass in soil as affected by pomegranate based multiple crop sequencing. <i>Scientia Horticulturae</i> , 197, pp.504-515.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study
Sheoran P, Sardana V and Singh S ; Chander S ; Kumar A ; Mann A ; Sharma P ;. (2017). Nutrient Management for Sustaining Productivity of Sunflower-Based Cropping Sequence in Indian Semiarid Regions. <i>Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis</i> , 48(5), pp.581-593.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 4-year study
Sherrid L A and McMaster G S; Delgado J A; Schipanski M E; Fonte S J; Monteneri R L; Larson K. (2018). Soil Carbon Pools in Dryland Agroecosystems as Affected by Several Years of Drought. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 47(4), pp.766-773.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR wheat–corn–fallow (WCF) and corn/sorghum [Sorghum bicolor (L.) Moench], wheat, hay millet, and sunflower (<i>Helianthus annuus</i>) (CC). No continuous monocrop, no legume, no perennial crop.
Shi X H and Yang X M; Drury C F; Reynolds W D; McLaughlin N B; Zhang X P;. (2012). Impact of ridge tillage on soil organic carbon and selected physical properties of a clay loam in southwestern Ontario. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 120, pp.1-7.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Tillage study. No data for corn-soybean vs. continuous corn.
Silvestro L B, Biganzoli F and Forjan H ; Albanesi A ; Arambarri A M; Manso L ; Moreno M V;. (2017). Mollisol: Biological Characterization under Zero Tillage with Different Crops Sequences. <i>Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology</i> , 19(1), pp.245-257.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Leguminous plants in all 5 rotations
Silvestro L B, Biganzoli F and Forjan H ; Albanesi A ; Arambarri A M; Manso L ; Moreno M V;. (2017). Mollisol: Biological characterization under zero tillage with different crops sequences. <i>Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology</i> , 19, pp.245-257.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Rotations with legumes and perennials
Sinaj S and Jeangros B . (2019). Preserving the sustainability of field crop systems: overview of 50 years of trials in Changins. <i>Agrarforschung Schweiz</i> , 10(2), pp.88-95.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION crop rotations only with annual crops
Singh K, Murphy BW and Marchant BP ;. (2013). Towards cost-effective estimation of soil carbon stocks at the field scale. <i>Soil Research</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation (wheat–canola–wheat–legume crop–wheat).
Singh R, Yaduvanshi N P. S and Singh K N; Kumar S ; Mishra V K; Singh Y P; Sharma D K;. (2014). Bio-chemical amelioration effects on physico-chemical dynamics of sodic soils under rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>) -wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>) cropping system. <i>Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences</i> , 84, pp.349-355.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Singh R N, Praharaj C S; Kumar R and Singh S S; Kumar N ; Singh U ;. (2018). Strengthening soil health under rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>) fallows in Eastern Plateau of India with dwarf rice and moisture conservation practices. <i>Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences</i> , 88(12), pp.61-70.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study (2011-2014)

Singh G, Schoonover J E and Williard K W. J; Kaur G ; Crim J ;. (2018). Carbon and Nitrogen Pools in Deep Soil Horizons at Different Landscape Positions. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 82(6), pp.1512-1525.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study, Climate Aw
Singh S, Yan S and Sorochan J ; Stier J ; Mayes M A; Zhuang J ; Jagadamma S ;. (2019). Soil Carbon Accumulation and Nutrient Availability in Managed and Unmanaged Ecosystems of East Tennessee. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 83(2), pp.458-465.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Sione S M. J, Wilson M G; Lado M and González A P;. (2017). Evaluation of soil degradation produced by rice crop systems in a Vertisol, using a soil quality index. <i>Catena</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Smith S F, Brye K R; Gbur E E; Chen P and Korth K ;. (2014). Residue and water management effects on aggregate stability and aggregate-associated carbon and nitrogen in a wheat-soybean, double-crop system. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 78, pp.1378-1391.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR One rotation only (winter wheat/soybean)
Smith S W, Johnson D and Quin S L. O; Munro K ; Pakeman R J; van der Wal ; R ; Woodin S J;. (2015). Combination of herbivore removal and nitrogen deposition increases upland carbon storage. <i>Global Change Biology</i> , 21, pp.3036-3048.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Smith E G and Janzen H H; Larney F J;. (2015). Long-term cropping system impact on quality and productivity of a Dark Brown Chernozem in southern Alberta. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 95, pp.177-186.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Smith E G, Janzen H H; Scherloski L and Larney F J; Ellert B H;. (2016). Long-term (47 yr) effects of tillage and frequency of summerfallow on soil organic carbon in a Dark Brown Chernozem soil in western Canada. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 96, pp.347-350.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Fallow wheat rotations only. Also not replicated.
Smith C J and Chalk P M;. (2018). The residual value of fertiliser N in crop sequences: An appraisal of 60 years of research using N-15 tracer. <i>Field Crops Research</i> , 217, pp.66-74.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Snapp S S, Grabowski P and Chikowo R ; Smith A ; Anders E ; Sitrine D ; Chimonyo V ; Bekunda M ;. (2018). Maize yield and profitability tradeoffs with social, human and environmental performance: Is sustainable intensification feasible?. <i>Agricultural Systems</i> , 162, pp.77-88.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Snowdon E, Zebarth B J and Burton D L; Goyer C ; Rochette P ;. (2013). Growing season N ₂ O emissions from two-year potato rotations in a humid environment in New Brunswick, Canada. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 93, pp.279-294.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 4-year study
Sofi J A and Bhat A G; Kirmai N A; Wani J A; Lone A H; Ganie M A; Dar G I. H;. (2016). Soil quality index as affected by different cropping systems in northwestern Himalayas. <i>Environmental Monitoring and Assessment</i> , 188, pp.1-13.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Sokouti Reza, Kaveh Athar and Mahdian Mohammad Hossein; Parvizi Yahya ;. (2017). Modeling of soil carbon storage capacity using farm management factors in drylands. <i>Agriculture & Forestry / Poljoprivreda i Sumarstvo</i> , 63(4), pp.153-165.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Regional study
Soman C, Li D and Wander M M; Kent A D;. (2017). Long-term fertilizer and crop-rotation treatments differentially affect soil bacterial community structure. <i>Plant and Soil</i> , 413(1-2), pp.145-159.	-Exclude on OUTCOME No SOC or OM data, Crop rotations not replicated
Somasundaram J, Singh R K and Prasad S N; Kumar A ; Ali S ; Sinha N K; Chaudhary R S; Mohanty M ; Lakaria B L; Sankar M ; Lal R ;. (2018). Effect of Soil Amendments and Land Use Systems on Surface Cracks, Soil Properties and Crop Yield in a Vertisol. <i>Agricultural Research</i> , 7(4), pp.443-455.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 4-year study
Somasundaram J, Chaudhary R S and Kumar D A; Biswas A K; Sinha N K; Mohanty M ; Hati K M; Jha P ; Sankar M ; Patra A K; Dalal R ; Chaudhari S K;. (2018). Effect of contrasting tillage and cropping systems on soil aggregation, carbon pools and aggregate-associated carbon in rainfed Vertisols. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 69(5), pp.879-891.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Somasundaram J, Salikram M and Sinha N K; Mohanty M ; Chaudhary R S; Dalal R C; Mitra N G; Blaise D ; Coumar M V; Hati K M; Thakur J K; Neenu S ; Biswas A K; Patra A K; Chaudhari S K;. (2019). Conservation agriculture effects on soil properties and crop productivity in a semiarid region of India. <i>Soil Research</i> , 57(2), pp.187-199.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study (2010-2013)
Sommer R, Ryan J and Masri S ; Singh M ; Diekmann J ;. (2011). Effect of shallow tillage, moldboard plowing, straw management and compost addition on soil organic matter and nitrogen in a dryland barley/wheat-vetch rotation. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 115-116, pp.39-46.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR No continuous cropping. Legumes in both rotations. No perennials.
Soussana J F and Lemaire G. (2014). Coupling carbon and nitrogen cycles for environmentally sustainable intensification of grasslands and crop-livestock systems. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 190, pp.9-17.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Souza L H. C, Matos E D; Magalhaes C A. D; de la Torre and E R ; Lamas F M; Lal R ;. (2018). Soil carbon and nitrogen stocks and physical properties under no-till and conventional tillage cotton-based systems in the Brazilian Cerrado. <i>Land Degradation & Development</i> , 29(10), pp.3405-3412.	-Exclude on CLIMATE

Sprunger C D and Robertson G P;. (2018). Early accumulation of active fraction soil carbon in newly established cellulosic biofuel systems. <i>Geoderma</i> , 318, pp.42-51.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 6-year study (2008-2013)
St Luce, M and Ziadi N ; Zebarth B J; Whalen J K; Grant C A; Gregorich E G; Lafond G P; Blackshaw R E; Johnson E N; O'Donovan J T; Harker K N;. (2013). Particulate organic matter and soil mineral nitrogen concentrations are good predictors of the soil nitrogen supply to canola following legume and non-legume crops in western Canada. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 93, pp.607-620.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 2-year study
Stehlikova I, Madaras M and Lipavsky J ; Simon T ;. (2016). Study on some soil quality changes obtained from long-term experiments. <i>Plant Soil and Environment</i> , 62, pp.74-79.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Fertilizer study, not possible to compare rotations based on reported data.
Storlien J O and Hons F M; Wight J P; Heilman J L;. (2014). Carbon Dioxide and Nitrous Oxide Emissions Impacted by Bioenergy Sorghum Management. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 78, pp.1694-1706.	-Exclude on OUTCOME CO2 gas flux
Stott D E and Cambardella C A; Karlen D L;. (2014). Assessment of Near-Surface Soil Carbon Content Across Several U. S. Cropland Watersheds. Dordrecht: Springer.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Studdert G A and Domingo M N; García G V; Monterubbianesi M G; Domínguez G F;. (2017). Soil organic carbon under contrasting cropping systems and its relationship with nitrogen supply capacity. <i>Ciencia del Suelo</i> , 35(2), pp.285-299.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Spanish
Sun H Y and Wang C X; Wang X D; Rees R M;. (2013). Changes in soil organic carbon and its chemical fractions under different tillage practices on loess soils of the Guanzhong Plain in north-west China. <i>Soil Use and Management</i> , 29, pp.344-353.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Sun B J and Jia S X; Zhang S X; McLaughlin N B; Liang A Z; Chen X W; Liu S Y; Zhang X P;. (2016). No tillage combined with crop rotation improves soil microbial community composition and metabolic activity. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> , 23, pp.6472-6482.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwa
Sundarapandian S M and Amritha S. (2015). Soil organic carbon stocks in different land uses at Puthupet, Tamil Nadu, India. <i>Research & ...</i> , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Swanepoel C M, Rotter R P; van der Laan and M ; Annandale J G; Beukes D J; du Preez ; C C ; Swanepoel L H; van der Merwe ; A ; Hoffmann M P;. (2018). The benefits of conservation agriculture on soil organic carbon and yield in southern Africa are site-specific. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 183, pp.72-82.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Syp A, Faber A and Pikula D ;. (2015). Assessing the impact of management practices on gas emissions and N losses calculated with denitrification-decomposition model. <i>Plant Soil and Environment</i> , 61, pp.433-437.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study
Taghizadeh-Toosi A, Olesen J E and Kristensen K ; Elsgaard L ; Ostergaard H S; Laegdsmand M ; Greve M H; Christensen B T;. (2014). Changes in carbon stocks of Danish agricultural mineral soils between 1986 and 2009. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 65, pp.730-740.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Regional study – not field study. In this case the relevant rotation types cannot be compared so it should be excluded.
Taghizadeh-Toosi A, Christensen B T and Hutchings N J; Vejlin J ; Katterer T ; Glendinning M ; Olesen J E;. (2014). C-TOOL: A simple model for simulating whole-profile carbon storage in temperate agricultural soils. <i>Ecological Modelling</i> , 292, pp.11-25.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Taghizadeh-Toosi A and Olesen J E. (2016). Modelling soil organic carbon in Danish agricultural soils suggests low potential for future carbon sequestration. <i>Agricultural Systems</i> , 145, pp.83-89.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Nation-wide modelling study
Tallis MJ, Casella E and Henshall PA ; Aylott MJ ;;. (2013). Development and evaluation of ForestGrowth-SRC a process-based model for short rotation coppice yield and spatial supply reveals poplar uses water more : Wiley Online Library.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study
Tammeorg P, Simojoki A and Mäkelä P ; Stoddard FL ;;. (2014). Biochar application to a fertile sandy clay loam in boreal conditions: effects on soil properties and yield formation of wheat, turnip rape and faba bean. <i>Plant and soil</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 3-year study
Tarui A, Matsumura A and Asakura S ; Yamawaki K ; Hattori R ; Daimon H ;. (2013). Evaluation of Mixed Cropping of Oat and Hairy Vetch as Green Manure for Succeeding Corn Production. <i>Plant Production Science</i> , 16, pp.383-392.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Mixed cropping study
Tekin S, Yazar A and Barut H ;. (2017). Comparison of wheat-based rotation systems and monocropping systems under dryland Mediterranean conditions. <i>International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering</i> , 10(5), pp.203-213.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 4-year study
Tellez-Rio A, Vallejo A and García-Marco S ; Martin-Lammerding D ; Tenorio J L; Rees R M; Guardia G ;. (2017). Conservation Agriculture practices reduce the global warming potential of rainfed low N input semi-arid agriculture. <i>European Journal of Agronomy</i> , 84, pp.95-104.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Theisen G, Silva J J. C and Silva J S; Andres A ; Anten N P. R; Bastiaans L ;. (2017). The birth of a new cropping system: towards sustainability in the subtropical lowland agriculture. <i>Field Crops Research</i> , 212, pp.82-94.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 9-year study (2006-2015)

Thomas CD, Anderson BJ and Moilanen A ; ;. (2013). Reconciling biodiversity and carbon conservation. <i>Ecology</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Thomas B W and Hao X Y; Willms W D;. (2017). Soil organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus 13 yr after abruptly disturbing Northern Great Plains grassland. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 97(2), pp.329-333.	-Exclude on OUTCOME no variation measures
Tits M, Elsen A and Bries J ; Vandendriessche H ;;. (2014). Short-term and long-term effects of vegetable, fruit and garden waste compost applications in an arable crop rotation in Flanders. <i>Plant and Soil</i> , 376, pp.43-59.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Only one rotation, no comparator
Tong Y X, Liu J G; Li X L; Sun J and Herzberger A ; Wei D ; Zhang W F; Dou Z X; Zhang F S;. (2017). Cropping System Conversion led to Organic Carbon Change in China's Mollisols Regions. <i>Scientific Reports</i> , 7, pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Multiple site survey, also climate Dwa/Dwb
Tongkoom K, Marohn C and Piepho H P; Cadisch G ;;. (2018). Ecosystem recovery indicators as decision criteria on potential reduction of fallow periods in swidden systems of Northern Thailand. <i>Ecological Indicators</i> , 95, pp.554-567.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Tortorella D, Scalise A and Pristeri A ; Petrovicova B ; Monti M ; Gelsomino A ;;. (2013). Chemical and biological responses in a Mediterranean sandy clay loam soil under grain legume-barley intercropping. <i>Agrochimica</i> , 57, pp.1-21.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Udawatta R P, Adhikari P and Senaviratne Gmma ; Garrett H E;. (2015). Variability of soil carbon in row crop watersheds with agroforestry buffers. <i>Agroforestry Systems</i> , 89, pp.37-47.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Buffer strip study, Only one rotation (corn-soybean).
Ukaew S, Beck E and Archer D W; Shonnard D R;. (2015). Estimation of soil carbon change from rotation cropping of rapeseed with wheat in the hydrotreated renewable jet life cycle. <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , 20, pp.608-622.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Modelling study using aggregated data
Upson M A and Burgess P J;. (2013). Soil organic carbon and root distribution in a temperate arable agroforestry system. <i>Plant and Soil</i> , 373, pp.43-58.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Tree (poplar) intercropping study
Van De Vreken , P and Gobin A ; Baken S ; Van Holm ; L ; Verhasselt A ; Smolders E ; Merckx R ;;. (2016). Crop residue management and oxalate-extractable iron and aluminium explain long-term soil organic carbon sequestration and dynamics. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 67, pp.332-340.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Crop residue study. Maize mono culture only (with cover crop rye grass). Permanent grass only available comparator.
VandenBygaert A J, Bremer E and McConkey B G; Janzen H H; Angers D A; Carter M R; Drury C F; Lafond G P; McKenzie R H;. (2010). Soil organic carbon stocks on long-term agroecosystem experiments in Canada. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 90, pp.543-550.	-Exclude on REVIEW
Veloso M G, Angers D A; Tiecher T and Giacomini S ; Dieckow J ; Bayer C ;;. (2018). High carbon storage in a previously degraded subtropical soil under no-tillage with legume cover crops. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 268, pp.15-23.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE
Veloso M G, Cecagno D and Bayer C ;;. (2019). Legume cover crops under no-tillage favor organomineral association in microaggregates and soil C accumulation. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 190, pp.139-146.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE
Venkatesh M S and Hazra K K; Ghosh P K; Praharaj C S; Kumar N. (2013). Long-term effect of pulses and nutrient management on soil carbon sequestration in Indo-Gangetic plains of India. <i>Canadian Journal of Soil Science</i> , 93, pp.127-136.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 7 year study
Venkatesh M S, Hazra K K; Ghosh P K; Khuswah B L; Ganeshamurthy A N; Ali M and Singh J ; Mathur R S;. (2017). Long-term effect of crop rotation and nutrient management on soil-plant nutrient cycling and nutrient budgeting in Indo-Gangetic plains of India. <i>Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science</i> , 63(14), pp.2007-2022.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Verloop J, Hilhorst G J and Pronk A A; Sebek L B; van Keulen ; H ; Janssen B H; Van Ittersum ; M K ;;. (2015). Organic matter dynamics in an intensive dairy production system on a Dutch Spodosol. <i>Geoderma</i> , 237, pp.159-167.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Two rotations with perennials, no comparator without perennials or with legumes.
Verma B C and Datta S P; Rattan R K; Singh A K;. (2013). Labile and stabilised fractions of soil organic carbon in some intensively cultivated alluvial soils. <i>Journal of Environmental Biology</i> , 34, pp.1069-1075.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Vieira F C. B, Bayer C and Zanatta J A; Mielniczuk J ; Six J ;;. (2009). Building up organic matter in a subtropical paleudult under legume cover-crop-based rotations. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 73, pp.1699-1706.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE One-year rotations only.
Vieira F C. B, Bayer C and Zanatta J ; Ernani P R;. (2009). Organic matter kept Al toxicity low in a subtropical no-tillage soil under long-term (21-year) legume-based crop systems and N fertilisation. <i>Australian Journal of Soil Research</i> , 47, pp.707-714.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-year rotations only
Villarino S H, Studdert G A; Baldassini P and Cendoya M G; Ciuffoli L ; Mastrangelo M ; Pineiro G ;;. (2017). Deforestation impacts on soil organic carbon stocks in the Semiarid Chaco Region, Argentina. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 575, pp.1056-1065.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Soil survey, deforestation study
Wade J, Horwath W R and Burger M B;. (2016). Integrating Soil Biological and Chemical Indices to Predict Net Nitrogen Mineralization across	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE

California Agricultural Systems. Soil Science Society of America Journal, 80, pp.1675-1687.	
Walia M K, Baer S G; Krausz R and Cook R L;. (2017). Deep soil carbon after 44 years of tillage and fertilizer management in southern Illinois compared to forest and restored prairie soils. Journal of Soil and Water Conservation, 72(4), pp.405-415.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR
Wang QK, Wang SL and Zhong MC ;. (2013). Ecosystem carbon storage and soil organic carbon stability in pure and mixed stands of Cunninghamia lanceolata and Michelia macclurei. Plant and soil, , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION monoculture vs. intercropping of tree species (Cunninghamia lanceolata and Michelia macclurei).
Wang G, Huang Y and Wang E ; Yu Y ; Zhang W ;. (2013). Modeling soil organic carbon change across Australian wheat growing areas, 1960–2010. : journals.plos.org.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Wang J and Sainju U M. (2014). Aggregate-Associated Carbon and Nitrogen Affected by Residue Placement, Crop Species, and Nitrogen Fertilization. Soil Science, 179, pp.153-165.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Wang Z G, Bao X G; Li X F; Jin X and Zhao J H; Sun J H; Christie P ; Li L ;. (2015). Intercropping maintains soil fertility in terms of chemical properties and enzyme activities on a timescale of one decade. Plant and Soil, 391, pp.265-282.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Bwk
Wang W F, Duan Y X; Zhang L X; Wang B and Li X J;. (2016). Effects of different rotations on carbon sequestration in Chinese fir plantations. Chinese Journal of Plant Ecology, 40, pp.669-678.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Chinese
Wang Y, Ji H F and Wang R ; Guo S L; Gao C Q;. (2017). Impact of root diversity upon coupling between soil C and N accumulation and bacterial community dynamics and activity: Result of a 30 year rotation experiment. Geoderma, 292, pp.87-95.	-Exclude on CLIMATE Cwa
Wang Y, Ji H and Wang R ; Guo S ; Gao C ;. (2017). Impact of root diversity upon coupling between soil C and N accumulation and bacterial community dynamics and activity: Result of a 30 year rotation experiment. Geoderma, 292, pp.87-95.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Wang J D and Wang K H; Wang X J; Ai Y C; Zhang Y C; Yu J G;. (2018). Carbon sequestration and yields with long-term use of inorganic fertilizers and organic manure in a six-crop rotation system. Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems, 111(1), pp.87-98.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR One rotation only (3-year rotation involving 6 crops)
Watanabe Y, Itanna F and Izumi Y ; Awala S K; Fujioka Y ; Tsuchiya K ; Iijima M ;. (2019). Cattle manure and intercropping effects on soil properties and growth and yield of pearl millet and cowpea in Namibia. Journal of Crop Improvement, 33(3), pp.395-409.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION The three cropping systems were: pearl millet mono-cropping, cowpea mono-cropping, and pearl millet-cowpea intercropping.
Watts D B and Torbert H A; Prior S A; Huluka G. (2010). Long-Term Tillage and Poultry Litter Impacts Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Mineralization and Fertility. Soil Science Society of America Journal, 74, pp.1239-1247.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION No rotation.
Wendt JW and Hauser S . (2013). An equivalent soil mass procedure for monitoring soil organic carbon in multiple soil layers. European Journal of Soil Science, , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Calculation method paper
Weyers S L, Archer D W; Forcella F and Gesch R ; Johnson J M. F;. (2018). Can reducing tillage and increasing crop diversity benefit grain and forage production?. Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems, 33(5), pp.406-417.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Whisler K M and Rowe H I; Dukes J S;. (2016). Relationships among land use, soil texture, species richness, and soil carbon in Midwestern tallgrass prairie, CRP and crop lands. Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment, 216, pp.237-246.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE soil survey
Whitbread A M and Blair G J; Lefroy R D. B;. (2000). Managing legume leys, residues and fertilisers to enhance the sustainability of wheat cropping systems in Australia: 2. Soil physical fertility and carbon. Soil and Tillage Research, , pp..	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Fertilizer and residue management study on chickpea (Cicer arietinum cv. Amethyst), barrel medic (Medicago truncatula cv. Sephi), lucerne (Medicago sativa cv. Trifecta) and a fallow system.
White C M, DuPont S T; Hautau M and Hartman D ; Finney D M; Bradley B ; LaChance J C; Kaye J P;. (2017). Managing the trade off between nitrogen supply and retention with cover crop mixtures. Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment, 237, pp.121-133.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Studies <10 years
Whitman T, Enders A and Lehmann J ;. (2014). Pyrogenic carbon additions to soil counteract positive priming of soil carbon mineralization by plants. Soil Biology and Biochemistry, , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Pot study
Whitmore A P and Kirk G J. D; Rawlins B G;. (2015). Technologies for increasing carbon storage in soil to mitigate climate change. Soil Use and Management, 31, pp.62-71.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Wienhold B J and Jin V L; Schmer M R; Varvel G E;. (2018). Soil Carbon Response to Projected Climate Change in the US Western Corn Belt. Journal of Environmental Quality, 47(4), pp.704-709.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Wiesmeier M, von Lutzow and M ; Sporlein P ; Geuss U ; Hangen E ; Reischl A ; Schilling B ; Kogel-Knabner I ;. (2015). Land use effects on organic	-Exclude on INTERVENTION

carbon storage in soils of Bavaria: The importance of soil types. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 146, pp.296-302.	
Wiesmeier M, Lungu M and Hubner R ; Cerbari V ;. (2015). Remediation of degraded arable steppe soils in Moldova using vetch as green manure. <i>Solid Earth</i> , 6, pp.609-620.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Wiesmeier M, Lungu M and Cerbari V ; Boincean B ; Hubner R ; Kogel-Knabner I ;. (2018). Rebuilding soil carbon in degraded steppe soils of Eastern Europe: The importance of windbreaks and improved cropland management. <i>Land Degradation & Development</i> , 29(4), pp.875-883.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Multiple site survey, crop rotation details unclear
Williams A, Jordan N R and Smith R G; Hunter M C; Kammerer M ; Kane D A; Koide R T; Davis A S;. (2018). A regionally-adapted implementation of conservation agriculture delivers rapid improvements to soil properties associated with crop yield stability. <i>Scientific Reports</i> , 8, pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Only 5 years
Winck B R, Vezzani F M; Dieckow J and Favaretto N ; Molin R ;. (2014). CARBON AND NITROGEN IN THE PARTICLE SIZE FRACTIONS OF SOIL ORGANIC MATTER IN CROP SYSTEMS UNDER NO-TILLAGE. <i>Revista Brasileira De Ciencia Do Solo</i> , 38, pp.980-989.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Portuguese. Same data as Alburquerque?
Wolf K, Herrera I and Tomich T P; Scow K ;. (2017). Long-term agricultural experiments inform the development of climate-smart agricultural practices. <i>California Agriculture</i> , 71(3), pp.120-124.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE Research brief with no data
Wood S L. R and Rhemtulla J M;. (2017). Cropping history trumps fallow duration in long-term soil and vegetation dynamics of shifting cultivation systems. <i>Ecological Applications</i> , 27(2), pp.519-531.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Wotherspoon A, Thevathasan N V and Gordon A M; Voroney R P;. (2014). Carbon sequestration potential of five tree species in a 25-year-old temperate tree-based intercropping system in southern Ontario, Canada. <i>Agroforestry Systems</i> , 88, pp.631-643.	-Exclude on COMPARATOR Study on effects of tree-based intercropping (TBI) on SOC. Only one rotation (corn-soybean-winter wheat/barley)
Wright A L and Hons F M;. (2005). Soil carbon and nitrogen storage in aggregates from different tillage and crop regimes. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 69, pp.141-147.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION This study does only compare continuous single crops
Wright A L, Dou F and Hons F M;. (2007). Crop species and tillage effects on carbon sequestration in subsurface soil. <i>Soil Science</i> , 172, pp.124-131.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION This study does only compare continuous single crops
Wright P J and Falloon R E; Hedderley D. (2017). A long-term vegetable crop rotation study to determine effects on soil microbial communities and soilborne diseases of potato and onion. <i>New Zealand journal of crop ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE 9-year study
Wu GL, Liu Y and Tian FP ; Shi ZH ;. (2016). Legumes functional group promotes soil organic carbon and nitrogen storage by increasing plant diversity. <i>Land Degradation & ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on CLIMATE Dwb
Wutzler T and Reichstein M . (2013). Priming and substrate quality interactions in soil organic matter models. <i>Biogeosciences</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE modelling study, no measured data reported
Wäldchen J, Schulze ED and Schönig I ;;. (2013). The influence of changes in forest management over the past 200years on present soil organic carbon stocks. <i>Forest Ecology and ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Forestry
Xavier C V, Moitinho M R; Teixeira D D; Santos G A. D; Barbosa M D; Milori Dmbp and Rigobelo E ; Cora J E; La Scala ; N ;. (2019). Crop rotation and succession in a no-tillage system: Implications for CO2 emission and soil attributes. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 245, pp.8-15.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Xu N, Wilson H F and Saiers J E; Entz M ;. (2013). Effects of Crop Rotation and Management System on Water-Extractable Organic Matter Concentration, Structure, and Bioavailability in a Chernozemic Agricultural Soil. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 42, pp.179-190.	-Exclude on OUTCOME
Xu X, Schimel JP and Thornton PE ; Song X ; Yuan F ; ;. (2014). Substrate and environmental controls on microbial assimilation of soil organic carbon: a framework for Earth system models. <i>Ecology ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Modelling study on C assimilation
Xu Y B, Qiu W W; Sun J P; Muller C and Lei B K;. (2019). Effects of wheat/faba bean intercropping on soil nitrogen transformation processes. <i>Journal of Soils and Sediments</i> , 19(4), pp.1724-1734.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Intercropping study
Yadav M R, Parihar C M; Jat S L; Singh A K; Kumar R and Yadav R K; Kuri B R; Parihar M D; Yadav B ; Verma A P; Jat M L;. (2017). Long term effect of legume intensified crop rotations and tillage practices on productivity and profitability of maize vis-a-vis soil fertility in North-Western Indo-Gangetic Plains of India. <i>Legume Research</i> , 40(2), pp.282-290.	-Exclude on CLIMATE BSh
Yadav G S, Lal R and Meena R S; Datta M ; Babu S ; Das A ; Layek J ; Saha P ;. (2017). Energy budgeting for designing sustainable and environmentally clean/safer cropping systems for rainfed rice fallow lands in India. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 158, pp.29-37.	-Exclude on CLIMATE -Exclude on STUDY TYPE
Yadav R P, Pal S and Arya S L; Sharma P ;. (2019). Tillage and brown manuring effects on soil properties and yield in Shivalik. <i>Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences</i> , 89(7), pp.121-124.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE -Exclude on CLIMATE
Yakutina O P and Nechaeva T V; Smirnovi N V;. (2015). Consequences of snowmelt erosion: Soil fertility, productivity and quality of wheat on	-Exclude on INTERVENTION

Greyzemic Phaeozem in the south of West Siberia. <i>Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment</i> , 200, pp.88-93.	
Yang J, Gao W and Ren S R;. (2015). Long-term effects of combined application of chemical nitrogen with organic materials on crop yields, soil organic carbon and total nitrogen in fluvo-aquic soil. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 151, pp.67-74.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Yannikos N, Leinweber P and Helgason B L; Baum C ; Walley F L; Van Rees ; K C J;. (2014). Impact of Populus trees on the composition of organic matter and the soil microbial community in Orthic Gray Luvisols in Saskatchewan (Canada). <i>Soil Biology & Biochemistry</i> , 70, pp.5-11.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION
Yao Z, Yan G and Zheng X ; Wang R ; Liu C ;. (2017). Straw return reduces yield-scaled N ₂ O plus NO emissions from annual winter wheat-based cropping systems in the North China Plain. <i>Science of the Total ...</i> , , pp..	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE -Exclude on COMPARATOR
Yin G L, Cai Z S; Tao R and Wu F ; Chen J G; Shi S L;. (2019). Effects of different crop rotations on soil nutrient, microorganism abundance and soil allelochemical levels in alfalfa. <i>Acta Prataculturae Sinica</i> , 28(3), pp.42-50.	-Exclude on CLIMATE
Yost J L and Egerton-Warburton L M; Schreiner K M; Palmer C E; Hartemink A E;. (2016). Impact of Restoration and Management on Aggregation and Organic Carbon Accumulation in Urban Grasslands. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 80, pp.992-1002.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Study of urban grassland sites that comprised a management chronosequence established within the Chicago Wilderness Land Management and Research Program
Yuan H C, Guo F X; Chen Y and Bai G ; Liang W ;. (2018). Effect of crop rotation patterns on field soil properties and medicinal material yield for <i>Angelicae sinensis</i> in alpine regions. <i>Acta Prataculturae Sinica</i> , 27(10), pp.183-193.	-Exclude on LANGUAGE Chinese
Zanatta J A, Bayer C and Dieckow J ; Vieira F C. B; Mielniczuk J ;. (2007). Soil organic carbon accumulation and carbon costs related to tillage, cropping systems and nitrogen fertilization in a subtropical Acrisol. <i>Soil and Tillage Research</i> , 94, pp.510-519.	-Exclude on LENGTH OF CYCLE 1-year rotations only.
Zhan M, Liska A J and Nguy-Robertson A L; Suyker A E; Pelton M P; Yang H S;. (2019). Modeled and Measured Ecosystem Respiration in Maize-Soybean Systems Over 10 Years. <i>Agronomy Journal</i> , 111(1), pp.49-58.	-Exclude on STUDY TYPE No reported measured SOC data.
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Zhu L Q and Hu N J; Yang M F; Zhan X H; Zhang Z W;. (2014). Effects of Different Tillage and Straw Return on Soil Organic Carbon in a Rice-Wheat Rotation System. Plos One, 9, pp..	-Exclude on INTERVENTION tillage and straw return study on a rice-wheat system
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Zuazo V H. D and Pleguezuelo C R. R; Tavira S C; Martinez J R. F;. (2014). Linking Soil Organic Carbon Stocks to Land-use Types in a Mediterranean Agroforestry Landscape. Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology, 16, pp.667-679.	-Exclude on INTERVENTION Comparison of eight different land use types, no detailed info on rotations.
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Redundanta artiklar

Citation	Reason for exclusion
Al-Kaisi M and Kwaw-Mensah D . (2016). Long-Term Tillage and Crop Rotation Effects on Soil Carbon and Soil Productivity in Northeast Iowa. Farm Progress Reports, , pp..	-Redundant Same data as in 29283651
Aller D M, Archontoulis S V; Zhang W D; Sawadgo W and Laird D A; Moore K ;. (2018). Long term biochar effects on corn yield, soil quality and profitability in the US Midwest. Field Crops Research, 227, pp.30-40.	-Redundant Same data as 43220758 Aller (2017)
Cates A M and Ruark M D;. (2017). Soil aggregate and particulate C and N under corn rotations: responses to management and correlations with yield. Plant and Soil, 415(1-2), pp.521-533.	-Redundant Duplicate, same as 29286037
Laudicina V A, Novara A and Gristina L ; Badalucco L ;. (2014). Soil carbon dynamics as affected by long-term contrasting cropping systems and tillages under semiarid Mediterranean climate. Applied Soil Ecology, 73, pp.140-147.	-Redundant Same data as Laudicina 2015 (29284665) which reports variance, so use that one.
Murage E W, Voroney P R; Kay B D; Deen B and Beyaert R P;. (2007). Dynamics and turnover of soil organic matter as affected by tillage. Soil Science Society of America Journal, 71, pp.1363-1370.	-Redundant Same study as in Murage (2008). Same data for corn but slightly different data for tobacco-rye. Use Murage (2008).

Exkluderade artiklar efter tillförlitlighetsgranskning

Citation	Reason for exclusion
Ashworth A J and Allen F L; DeBruyn J M; Owens P R; Sams C. (2018). Crop Rotations and Poultry Litter Affect Dynamic Soil Chemical Properties and Soil Biota Long Term. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 47(6), pp.1327-1338.	-Essential data missing Not possible to separate effect of different cover crops. Confounding factor.
Berti A, Morari F and Dal Ferro ; N ; Simonetti G ; Polese R ;. (2016). Organic input quality is more important than its quantity: C turnover coefficients in different cropping systems. <i>European Journal of Agronomy</i> , 77, pp.138-145.	-Essential data missing No variability reported
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Duval M E, Galantini J A; Iglesias J O; Canelo S and Martinez J M; Wall L ;. (2013). Analysis of organic fractions as indicators of soil quality under natural and cultivated systems. <i>Soil & Tillage Research</i> , 131, pp.11-19.	-Essential data missing No details on different rotations, intervention duration not reported.
Fan J L and McConkey B G; Janzen H H; Miller P R;. (2018). Energy and energy analysis as an integrative indicator of sustainability: A case study in semi-arid Canadian farmlands. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 172, pp.428-437.	-Essential data missing No variability reported.
Farina R, Di Bene and C ; Piccini C ; Marchetti A ; Troccoli A ; Francaviglia R ;. (2018). Do Crop Rotations Improve the Adaptation of Agricultural Systems to Climate Change? A Modeling Approach to Predict the Effect of Durum Wheat-Based Rotations on Soil Organic Carbon and Nitrogen. <i>World Soil Resources Report No. 106</i> . In: , ed., <i>Soil Management and Climate Change: Effects on Organic Carbon, Nitrogen Dynamics, and Greenhouse Gas Emissions</i> . : , pp.221-236.	-Essential data missing The study area is fine, but the book chapter do not give us the info we need - but it will be there somewhere - Italy study
Jarecki M, Grant B and Smith W ; Deen B ; Drury C ; VanderZaag A ; Qian B D; Yang J Y; Wagner-Riddle C ;. (2018). Long-term Trends in Corn Yields and Soil Carbon under Diversified Crop Rotations. <i>Journal of Environmental Quality</i> , 47(4), pp.635-643.	-Essential data missing
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